

TATA POWER SOLAR

A Project Report on

“PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED SOLAR PV POWER PLANT IN INDIA”

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CHAPTER 1 - INTRODUCTION

1.1 Solar Energy

There is a pressing need to accelerate the development of advanced clean energy technologies in order to address the global challenges of energy security, climate change and sustainable development. Solar Photovoltaic is a key technology option to realize the shift to a decarbonised energy supply and is projected to emerge as an attractive alternate electricity source in the future. At the beginning of 2017, research has predicted that solar is on course to become the world's cheapest source of energy within the next 10 years. The dramatically falling costs from the supply chain to the final product could see the average global price become cheaper than coal within the next 10 years, according to Bloomberg New Energy Finance (BNEF) Data firms are predicting immense growth in solar power generation for 2018, forecasting installations to hit 108 GW by the end of the year. These growth trends are continuing and is likely to explode once the grid parity is achieved.

India is located in the equatorial sun belt of the earth, thereby receiving abundant radiant energy from the sun. The India Meteorological Department (IMD) maintains a nationwide network of radiation stations which measure solar radiation and also the daily duration of sunshine. In most parts of India, clear sunny weather is experienced 250 to 300 days a year.

India's solar industry is constantly growing. As of the end of November, 2017, the country has installed around 5.5 GW of PV, and is rapidly paving the way to becoming a world leader in the industry. Overall, the country saw a rapid increase in renewable energy activity, with solar dominating almost 48% share of total capacity installed.

Performance optimization of a 50 MW working SPV plant has been done for this project, and a set of site specific improvements have been proposed for the major performance and operational issues in this plant. The scope of these suggestions can be further broadened to apply to other working SPV plants. For better comprehension of the topic, and to consider all possible ways to optimize performance of PV system, literature review of the topics was done, along with a detailed loss analysis using a simulated PVsyst model and SCADA data. This has helped in streamlining the topic and helped in conceptualization of the techniques to measure and optimize the performance at different fronts.

For further understanding, fundamentals related to performance evaluation and PV technology have been covered briefly.

1.1.1 Solar Energy potential

Solar Energy unlike any other energy is available at almost all places on earth. The places lying in between the tropic of Cancer and tropic of Capricorn witness the highest magnitude of sunlight and for maximum time of the year. The image below shows the total global irradiation in India.

Figure 1: Irradiation Map of India

1.1.2 Solar Terms

- 1. Solar Irradiance:** Irradiance is the instantaneous amount of energy falling on per unit area of a surface. It is expressed in Watt per meter square (W/ m²). It is sometimes called as Intensity of radiation falling on a surface.
- 2. Irradiation (kWh/m²/day):** Irradiation is the amount of energy, which can be generated per meter square of area in a particular time. Irradiation is dependent on the irradiance falling at a location and the time for which energy is generated.
- 3. Energy Generation Efficiency:** Energy generation from sunlight depends on the conversion technology. The c-Si photovoltaic technology which is primarily being used everywhere has the conversion efficiency of only 15-20% (based on current technology used).

1.2 Performance Measures for PV Modules:

1. Standard Temperature Conditions (STC)

STC conditions are set of ideal conditions at which performance of different types of solar modules is compared. The temperature at STC is 25°C, 1.5 Air Mass and 1000W/m² irradiance. These conditions can be attained in lab only. For irradiance a sun simulator is used and cooling system is used to keep the temperature of cell at 25°C. On earth's surface we receive irradiation equivalent to AM 1.5 irradiation.

2. Normal Operating Cell Temperature (NOCT)

NOCT is set of conditions, which are more close to real world conditions. These give a more informed picture about the performance of a cell. At NOCT, irradiance is 800W/m² and ambient temperature is considered to be 20°C with a wind flowing at 1m/s speed. Each module manufacturer specifies temperature of the cell manufactured at his facility at the above environmental conditions.

The empirical relation for cell temperature is:

$$T_{cell} = T_{amb} + \frac{(NOCT - 20) * G}{800}$$

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Modules in the TP250 series TP240 TP245 TP250 TP255 TP260

Electrical parameters at standard test conditions (STC)*

	TP240	TP245	TP250	TP255	TP260
Nominal power output (W)	240	245	250	255	260
Power tolerance (W)	0 ~ +5	0 ~ +5	0 ~ +5	0 ~ +5	0 ~ +5
Module efficiency ($\eta\%$)	14.40	14.70	15.00	15.30	15.60
Voltage at P_{MAX} V_{MPP} (V)	29.7	29.9	30.2	30.4	30.6
Current at P_{MAX} I_{MPP} (A)	8.10	8.20	8.30	8.40	8.49
Open-circuit voltage V_{OC} (V)	36.5	36.7	37.3	37.5	37.9
Short-circuit current I_{SC} (A)	8.68	8.70	8.71	8.76	8.80

Electrical parameters at NOCT

	TP240	TP245	TP250	TP255	TP260
Power output P_{MAX} (W)	172.8	176.4	180.0	183.6	187.2
Voltage at P_{MAX} V_{MPP} (V)	26.3	26.4	26.7	26.9	27.1
Current at P_{MAX} I_{MPP} (A)	6.58	6.67	6.74	6.83	6.91
Open-circuit voltage V_{OC} (V)	32.5	32.7	32.8	32.8	32.9
Short-circuit current I_{SC} (A)	7.17	7.27	7.35	7.45	7.55

Temperature coefficient characteristics

NOCT ($^{\circ}C$)	47 \pm 2
Module efficiency ($\%/^{\circ}C$)	-0.06 \pm 0.01
Temperature coefficient of P_{MAX} ($\%/^{\circ}C$)	-0.4383
Temperature coefficient of V_{OC} ($\%/^{\circ}C$)	-0.3305
Temperature coefficient of I_{SC} ($\%/^{\circ}C$)	0.0638

Operating conditions

Maximum system voltage (UL & IEC) (V)	600 & 1000
Maximum series fuse rating (A)	20
Limiting reverse current (A)	20
Operating temperature range ($^{\circ}C$)	-40 and +85
Maximum static load (snow or wind)	113 psf (5400 Pa)

Module general characteristics

Module dimensions L x W x H (mm)	1666 x 1000 x 40
Module weight (approx) (kg [lbs])	19.4 [42.8]
Number of cells & size	60 cells & 156mm
Frame material	Anodized aluminium
Glass	3.2mm ARC
Junction box	IP67 rated
Cable connector	MC4 compatible (4mm ²)

Packaging details

Number of modules per pallet	26
Number of pallets per 40ft container	28
Box weight (kg)	605
Box dimensions L x W x H (mm)	1700 x 1165 x 1200

Technical Drawing** Dimensions in mm

IV curve at multiple temperatures

IV curve at multiple irradiance

* Irradiance of 1000W/m², spectrum AM of 1.5 and cell temperature of 25 $^{\circ}C$
Best in class AAA solar simulator (IEC 60904-9) used, power measurement tolerance \pm 3%

** Tolerance for dimensions -3/+3mm
Tolerance for cable length 0/+50mm

Listed specifications are subject to change without notice

Table 1: Specification sheet of a Tata Power Solar Multi-crystalline module

1.3 Solar Power Plants

A solar power plant is based on the conversion of sunlight into electricity using photovoltaics (PV)

1. General aspects of solar energy

Sun has been a primary source of energy for last millions of years. The need to switch from fossil fuel to renewable sources have again reminded us of sun's huge energy capacity. We use semi-conductors to convert sun light to electricity.

1. PV Fundamentals

Photovoltaic technology has been in market for a very long time. Because of its huge cost its use was strictly limited to army and satellite applications. The conversion of sunlight to electricity takes place by a phenomenon known as photoelectric effect. In this photons with electromagnetic energy strikes on the surface of a semiconductor and if the band gap of semiconductor matches with the energy of photon, the electrons get excited to higher energy states. This generation of electrons and holes, can now suitably be transferred via an electric circuit, which is known as current.

1.3.1 Types of SPV Projects:

1. Utility Scale Solar Power Plant:

Utility scale SPV plant implies that the power plant is giving power to state or central transmission utility. This term is very commonly used for SPV projects, which supply electricity to grid at 33kV or more. These projects are of large sizes generally comparative to size of typical coal and hydro power plants.

2. Ultra-Mega Solar Power Projects:

Ultra-Mega Solar Power project is a single power project with capacity of over 500 MW. These projects may be set up in some of these Solar Parks. The projects may be bid out after developing the park or simultaneously with park developments. In some cases, the full park may be one Ultra Mega Project.

Note: For simplicity, we can divide the large SPV plant into two sides. DC side and AC side of a solar power plant. The DC side will cover all the components where DC electricity is flowing. AC side will cover the areas where AC supply is there.

1.3.2 Components of SPV Power Plants

A Utility scale solar PV system consists of the following components:

1. DC Side:

- PV Modules
- Mounting Structures
- Tracking System (optional)
- DC Cables
- String Fuses
- Array Junction Box/ String Monitoring Box
- Array Fuse
- DC breakers

2. AC Side:

- Solar Inverter
- LT Panel with bus-bar
- Air Circuit Breaker
- Multi-function electric meters
- Transformer
- HT panel with bus-bar
- Feeder bus-bars
- Isolator Yard/Electricity Evacuation point for solar plant

3. Grid Side AC component: (stepping up the voltages)

- Pooling Substation (energy from different types of plant is pooled at one location)
- Distribution company sub-station (sometimes 1&2 are together)
- Transmission Company Sub-station (to maintain grid stability)

Now, this electricity is transferred to National grid, which can now be used across the nation.

4. Components of a small off-grid system: (Standalone or Grid connected)

- PV Generator (PV Panels/ Modules)
- Battery
- Charge controller (needed only when batteries are used to prevent overcharging of batteries)
- Inverter/ converter
- Mounting structure
- Tracking system (need not always be required)
- Wire and cable for connections

1.3.3 Parameters affecting the electricity generation from a SPV plant

- 1) PV Technology
- 2) Individual Component Efficiency
 - a) Inverter Efficiency
 - b) Transformer Efficiency
 - c) AC/ DC wire Efficiency
 - d) Auxiliary consumption in electrical and electronic equipment
- 3) Irradiance -On-site irradiance
- 4) Environmental Factors
 - a) PV Module temperature
 - b) Ambient Air Temperature
 - c) Wind speed and direction
 - d) Soiling ratio
 - e) Rainfall
 - f) Snow
 - g) Humidity

1.4 Losses Involved in a solar power plant

Below are the factors responsible for the lower efficiency of the complete system:

- Temperature of the solar module
- Dirt or soiling on face of solar module
- Manufacturer's tolerance
- Voltage drop through AC and DC cabling
- Inverter efficiency/ loss
- Shading
- Tilt angle of the solar modules
- Orientation of solar modules

1.4.1 Detailed losses

Thermal Parameter

Check the “Free” mounted modules with air circulation since we are placing them out in a field.

1) DC Cable Losses

DC cable losses are mainly due to the power losses (I^2R losses) and voltage drop through the cable.

Power Loss depends on the size, length and current passing through the cable. The specific resistivity of the cable used is another deciding factor for power losses. It is therefore imperative to minimize the cable length used, increase conductor size as well as reduce the amount of current passing through the conductor.

Voltage drop depends on the material of conductor used, ampere capacity, conductor size and conductor length.

2) AC Cable Losses

AC Cable Losses are due to skin effect and dielectric losses.

Skin effect takes place in high frequency signal transmission in cables. At high frequencies, the signal tends to propagate along the surface of the inner conductor.

This skin depth (δ) is defined by

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2\rho}{\omega\mu}}$$

Where ω frequency in rad/s is, μ is the conductor's electric permeability in H/m and ρ is the conductor's resistance in ohmmeters.

The resistance per unit length, R_l is defined by

$$R_l = \frac{\rho}{\omega\delta} = \frac{1}{\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\omega\mu}{2\rho}}$$

3) Ohmic losses

It is the ratio of the wiring ohmic loss $P_w = R_w * I_{sc}^2$ compared to the nominal power P_{nom} (array) = $R_{array} * I_{sc}^2$.

Where

$$R_{array} = V_{mp} / I_{mp} \text{ at STC}$$

R_w = global wiring resistance of the full system.

This is computed for a given sub-array (an inverter MPPT input) as the resistance of all strings wires in parallel, in series with the cables from the intermediate connection box on the roof to the inverter input. The global wiring resistance R_w of the system is obtained by putting all the sub-array wiring resistances in parallel.

The AC wiring losses may simply be defined by the distance between the inverter output and the injection point. The program will determine the minimum section of the wires, and only propose suitable sections if you want to increase it.

Inversely you can also specify a loss fraction at STC, and according to the chosen wire section, the corresponding wire length will appear, as well as the voltage drop at STC.

If several subsystems are defined, this AC loss may either be defined separately for each subsystem, or globally for the whole system.

If an external transformer is involved, the AC loss may be computed either on the low-voltage side (between the Inverter(s) and the transformer) or on the high voltage side (output of the transformer).

4) Transformer Losses

The main losses associated with the transformer are:

- The iron losses (mostly due to hysteresis and eddy currents in the core) are proportional to the square of the core flux, i.e. to the square of the voltage. As we have a constant grid voltage, this is considered as a constant loss. PVsyst proposes a default value of 0.1% of the nominal power.
- The ohmic losses are either in the primary or in the secondary windings. These may be represented by an equivalent resistance, and the loss will be computed as $R * I^2$ during the simulation.

Therefore the yearly resistive loss will always be lower (in percentage) than the nominal loss at STC.

5) Module Quality - LID - Mismatch

LID -Light Induced Degradation

- Initial degradation of solar PV module occurs in the very first hours of operation on the actual site. After certain period of time the power output of the module stabilizes.

Typically Polycrystalline Si module degrades is at 1%

Mono crystalline Si module degrades at 1.5%

Thin film module degrades is at 2%.

6) Mismatch loss

The mismatch losses is mainly due to the fact that in a string of modules the lowest current drives the current of the whole string. This is due to the material property of silicon which is used for the PV module manufacturing. The mismatch losses are constant.

7) Power loss at MPP

The difference b/n the effective operation conditions as the maximum available power point. Its value is typically limited to 1%.

8) Soiling losses

- Accumulation of dirt and its effect on system performance is an uncertainty which strongly depends on the environment of the system, raining conditions.
- Soiling losses vary according to the geography for example, in Rajasthan the power loss can be upto 3% and in regions like Karnataka its upto 2%.The power loss can be reduced by increasing frequency of module cleaning

9) IAM losses

IAM stands for Incidence Angle Modifier. The incidence effect corresponds to the decrease of the irradiance really reaching the PV cells surface, with respect to irradiance under normal incidence. This decrease is mainly due to reflexions on the glass cover, which increases with the incidence angle. The transmission loss is a general phenomenon, due to the reflexion and transmission of the sun's ray at each material interface (air-glass, glass-EVA, EVA-cell), as well as some absorption in the glass. This arises for any incidence ray. For normal incidence, the reflexion is of the order of 5%, and is included in the measured STC performance. The IAM only concerns the angular dependency of this effect, i.e. it is normalized to the transmission at perpendicular incidence (0° incidence angle).

10) Auxiliaries

The auxiliary energy are any electrical energy subtracted from the energy pushed to the grid for powering any equipment onsite.

11) Aging

The main parts of a PV system subjected to ageing are:

- The PV module (long-term degradation)
- The batteries in systems with storage (should be replaced, sometimes several times during the life of a system)
- Eventually the inverters, which have sometimes to be repaired or replaced
- Elements of the wiring, lightning surge protectors, etc.

The PV module degradation gives rise to a progressive loss of efficiency, which we will characterize by a "Degradation Loss factor". People often use the Manufacturer's warranty as loss reference when designing PV systems, which is usually a loss of efficiency of around 20% after 25 years.

12) Unavailability

System unavailability can be defined as a fraction of time, or a number of days. As this is usually unpredictable, you have the opportunity of defining specific periods of unavailability of the system, and also to create these periods in a random way. The effective energy loss is of course depending on the season and the weather during the unavailability periods.

**CHAPTER 2 - SITE
DETAILS AND
PERFORMANCE
ANALYSIS**

2.1. Introduction

Increasing energy demand and depletion of conventional sources have triggered the scientists to pave way for the development of research in the field of renewable energy sources especially solar energy.

For the suggestion of site specific improvements a detailed study of the PV plant under consideration was done using a simulated PVsyst model and SCADA and other plant data for the year 2016-2017.

The analysis of the performance of the 50 MWp grid connected solar photovoltaic power plant was carried out with the following objectives:

1. To identify and quantify the losses at the working PV plant over the year 2016-2017 and thereby improve its performance by optimizing the working of the plant.
2. To study the seasonal variations in PV plant output from the monitored SCADA data system.
3. To evaluate the technical performance through estimation of annual energy yield, array yield, reference yield and system losses.
4. To compare the actual performance data and calculated losses with the simulated data of PVsyst.
5. To use the losses

2.2. Description of the solar PV-GRID system

The grid-connected PV system consists of solar panels, inverters, a power conditioning unit and grid connection equipment. It has effective utilization of power that is generated from solar energy as there are no energy storage losses. When conditions are right, the grid-connected PV system supplies the excess power, beyond consumption by the connected load to the utility grid. But, in stand-alone systems batteries are used to store energy or else energy has to be directly connected to load.

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of 50 MW solar plant

2.2.1. Geographical location of the site

The solar power plant is situated in southern part of India and receives very good amount of sunlight throughout the year with an average ambient temperature of 40°C. It is located in a geographically convenient location where rainfall is quite unpredictable and due to poor soil condition agriculture is discouraged. The plant is setup in a barren and a waste land and does not affect vegetation of the area thus maintaining an ecological balance.

2.2.2. Plant layout

The total rating of the plant is 50 MW occupied over 256 acres of land. This plant area is divided into thirteen different blocks. Each individual block has an inverter room with a generating capacity of about 4 MW from twelve rooms and 2 MW from the thirteenth room, thus total of thirteen rooms combined to form a 50 MW generation capacity. Each block of solar panels consists of a total of 4160 strings.

These large numbers of solar panels in single block are again divided into two blocks of strings. Each string consists of 48 solar panels connected in series-parallel combination using Y connectors. Each structure consists of 24 panels and about 16 of these structures are connected to a string monitoring box which is connected to an inverter. Three phases double fed primary winding transformer is used, converted AC power from the two inverters is fed to these two primaries of the transformer. Each string consists of 48 modules in that way 8 strings are connected to one string monitoring box (SMB). Total 8 SMB'S are connected to one inverter. Total 50 inverters are connected to one transformer. The output of transformer is connected directly to 33 kV grid.

The plant is installed in such a way that it is cost effective, more reliable and gives out more energy output. During nights when there is no power generation due to lack of solar irradiation,

power is drawn from grid for internal power requirement. The power is utilized for lighting, initial starting of the batteries, and control room appliances among others.

2.2.3. Tilt angle

The tilt angle is considered according to the geographical location of the plant to get maximum solar radiation. The tilt is made equal to the latitude of area. It is designed in such a way that manual seasonal tilt technology is used in order to absorb more solar radiation and to extract greater power output. The tilting of the solar panels is done twice a year and is arranged as follows. From October to March as it is the winter season at the site the tilt should be somewhat higher, and is about 27° and from April to October the tilt is of lesser value, about 3° , as it is summer season.

2.2.4 Specification and Installation of solar arrays

The solar panels mounted at the 50 MW solar power plant are of 250Wp rating and made up of polycrystalline silicon. These panels have an efficiency of 18.6% and are of fixed type. Polycrystalline panel ratings are open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of 37 V and short circuit current (I_{SC}) of 8.92 A. It has a maximum operating temperature of 43.2° centigrade.

The solar panels are installed in such a way that structure to structure and leg centre to centre distance is at 4 m. The panel to panel distance is of 25 mm. Distance between grounds to lower edge of the module is 400 mm. To have a better yield panels are cleaned twice in a month.

2.2.5. Power conditioning units

Inverters are used to convert DC power into AC power. The inverter power rating is 1 MW and works with an efficiency of 97% to 98%. It can withstand a maximum load of 1.25 MW. It has a switching frequency of 300 kHz. PV voltage of 874 V and supply DC current 845 A is fed as input to inverter. The output AC voltage and current from inverter are 350 V and 1040 A respectively. The output of the inverter is synchronized automatically with same voltage and frequency as that of grid.

2.2.6. Power evacuation

The rated power of the transformer is 4 MVA and manufacture type is of Vector group DY5Y5. The primary voltage of the transformer is 385 V and secondary is directly connected to 33 kV switchyard. The efficiency of transformer is almost 97%.

2.2.7. Data monitoring

A weather monitoring station is located next to the plant which records the wind speed, ambient temperature and solar radiation data. A supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) with a dedicated server is present for assessment of the monitored data. The server records the data of voltage, current, power factor, power output of inverters, the solar irradiance, wind speed and ambient temperature data received from automatic weather station for each and every minute. The server collects the data from measuring sensors and at the outgoing side of the inverters through bus. It transfers the data files periodically and the server retrieves the data. Server along with the SCADA software is located in a control room.

Site Details					
Country		India			
Company		TATA Power Solar			
Purpose		Power generation and distribution to state utility grid			
Site and Meteo Details			Project Details		
Ambient Temperature(°C)	Max	Avg	Min	Estimated array peak power	50MW
	54	25	20		
Phase connection	3-phase		Shading consideration	Shade free	
Daily Solar irradiation-Horizontal	6.89 kWh/m ²		Grid voltage	33kV	
Wind speed	2-15 m/s		Grid frequency	50Hz	
Earth Temperature(°C)	Max	Avg	Min	Available/required area	2 km ² (Approx.)
	40	26	26		

Table 2: Site Details

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
SOLAR PV POWER PLANT IN INDIA | 2017-2018

System overview			
SPV array peak power		258Wp	
No. of SPV strings		8320	
Connections of PV module in each string		Series(12) and parallel	
Inverter		1MW	
Inverter type/Topology		Centralized	
Total no. of inverters		50	
Modular components			
Components	Specification	Quantity	Make
Solar PV modules	Max Peak Power= 258Wp	199992	TATA Power Solar
Non-modular components			
Components	Specification	Quantity	Make
Inverters	1MW	50	ABB
Transformers	4MVA, 3- ϕ , 33kV, Power transformer	13	
SCADA/Monitoring system	(Integrated and remote monitoring system)	1	Rockwell
Switch gear	Rated voltage:33kV; Current(Max):1000A;SCwithstand capacity:315A /1250V;Dynamic capacity:1250 kA/3 sec	35	ABB
Isolator	V _{MAX} =430V Max cont. current=100A	13	L &T

Table 3: PV panel design

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
SOLAR PV POWER PLANT IN INDIA | 2017-2018

Required electrical characteristics of SPV modules	
Watt peak	258W
V _{OC}	37V
V _{MPP}	35.15 V
I _{SC}	8.92A
I _{MPP}	8.474
Module efficiency/module area	18.6%
Power tolerance	±2.5%
Technology	Polycrystalline
No. of cells	60 and 72
Required operating condition details	
Maximum fuse rating	30A
Operating temperature range	30-55 °C
Required temperature co-efficient characteristics at STP	
NOCT (°C)	45±2
Module efficiency(%/ °C)	18.6%
Solar PV array sizing and connection details	
Conditions	At avg. ambient temperature (28 °C)
Watt peak of each SPV module	240-258Wp
Total no. of SPV module required	199992

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Total no. of strings	8320
No. of SPV modules in each string	48
String voltage (V_{MPP})	650V
String current (I_{SC}/I_{MPP})	16-20A
Connections of string	Series-parallel
Array voltage (V_{OC}/V_{MPP})	800/650V
Array current (I_{SC}/I_{MPP})	8/16A
Inverter Type	String inverter (MMPT)
Quantity	50
INPUT (DC)	
Max power	1MW
Max absolute input voltage	800V
Start voltage	550V
Nominal MPP voltage range	650V
Max input current per string	20A
No. of independent MPP inputs/strings	4096
OUTPUT (AC)	
Rated output power	1MW
Power threshold	1.25MW
Nominal AC voltage/range	380V

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
SOLAR PV POWER PLANT IN INDIA | 2017-2018

AC power frequency/range	50 Hz
Max output power	900-950 kW
Power factor at rated power	Almost unity
Feed-in phase/ connection phases	3-phase 6 cables per phase
EFFICIENCY	
Max efficiency	97
PROTECTION DETAILS	
Protection class	Class B or Class C
Operating temperature range	85 °C
Self-consumption	65 W at sleep mode
Cooling option	Air cooling fan
INVERTER CONNECTION DETAILS	
Total no. of inverters	50
No. of strings per inverter	85
Connection of strings/inverter	Parallel
Inter-inverter connection	Parallel
Transformer sizing	
Transformer type	Power transformer
Cooling type	Oil Natural and Air Natural
Rated kVA	4MVA
High voltage rating	33kV

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
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Low voltage rating	380V	
Operating frequency	50 Hz	
Tap changer	Off load tap-changer	
Protective devices		
Components	Specification	Quantity
DC disconnects	2 pole (As per IEC)	16 fuses
Switchgear	Rated voltage=33kV Rated main busbar current (Max)=1000A	
Circuit breakers (MCCB)	Inverter to busbar Busbar/panel box to transformer	35 Vacuum CB and 50 Air CB
Main isolator (HT side)		
Design criteria	IS-9921/IEC-129	
Operating frequency	50Hz±3%	
Nominal system voltage	33W	
Max system voltage	36kV	
Rated SC current for 3s	1250A	

Table 4: PV System Design

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
SOLAR PV POWER PLANT IN INDIA | 2017-2018

DC side cables	
Design criteria	240 mm ² and 300 mm ²
Cable material	PVC (Polycab)
Single cable length per string to inverter	80m
Cross section per string	Single core
Conductor type	Copper
Insulation material	XL DPE
LT cables (Inverters to busbar/distribution panel)	
Design criteria	50 mm ²
Cross section	4 core, 50 m ²
Max withstand current capacity	50 A
Conductor type	Copper
HT cables (from distribution panel to feed-in point)	
Design criteria	600 mm ²
Cable material	XL DPE (Polycab)
Cable length from distribution panel to feed-in point	250m
Cross section	3 core, 600mm ²
SC withstand current capacity	1250 A
Insulation material	XL DPE

Busbar constructional analysis					
Busbar material	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Main busbar</th> <th>Auxiliary busbar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Copper with Aluminium coating</td> <td>Copper with Aluminium coating</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Main busbar	Auxiliary busbar	Copper with Aluminium coating	Copper with Aluminium coating
	Main busbar	Auxiliary busbar			
Copper with Aluminium coating	Copper with Aluminium coating				
Busbar length	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Main busbar</th> <th>Auxiliary busbar</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>60m</td> <td>5-6m</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Main busbar	Auxiliary busbar	60m	5-6m
	Main busbar	Auxiliary busbar			
60m	5-6m				
Earthing busbar material	Aluminium with Silver coating				

Table 5: Cable design

Earthing and lightning protection	
Design criteria	45 lightning arrestor and normal earthing with regular maintenance
Earth electrode sizing	
Physical parameters	Copper
Material	Charcoal, salt
Min depth of earth pit	5m
Components grounding	Charcoal, water
Lightning protection	
Design criteria	Lightning arrestors
Sizing	20m

Table 6: Earthing and Lighting Protection

PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF AN EXISTING 50MW GRID CONNECTED
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PV tilted angle (optimized)	3 °C-Summer and 27 °C-Winter
Mounting type	Ground mounting
Overall dimension	250 Acres (50MW)
Foundation	Concrete
Wind load	2-15m/s
Fixing type	Stainless steel

Table 7: PV Array mounting and constructional details

Total land required= 256 Acres

Overall power plant performance summary

Total no of PV modules	199992
Total no of inverters	50
Max DC input per inverter	1MW
Nominal PV power	50MW
Max PV power output	46MW
Nominal AC power	46MW
Max operating power at STC	41MW
Max operating power at ambient temperature	55
Plant production	50 MW
Performance ratio	76%

Table 8: Overall power plant performance summary

2.3. Methodology for performance analysis of the PV system

The performance of grid connected solar photovoltaic power plant is divided in three stages.

- (1) Manually extract the parameters of power generation through SCADA system.
- (2) Calculate the performance ratio and system losses of the power plant with the help of the data.
- (3) Compare the performance with PVsyst based plant design.

International Energy Agency (IEA) has developed the performance parameters for analysing the performance of solar PV grid interconnected system. Many performance parameters are used to define the overall system performance with respect to the energy production, solar resource and overall effect of system losses. The various parameters are the performance ratio, final PV system yield and reference yield.

2.4. Simulation based on PV plant under study using PVsyst software

2.4.1. Simulation using PVsyst

PVsyst software is one of the simulation software developed to estimate the performance of the solar power plant by importing meteo data from many different sources as well as personnel data. This software evaluates the performance of grid-connected, stand-alone and pumping systems based on the specified module selection. The program accurately predicts the system yields computed using detailed hourly simulation data. [12]

In this study PVsyst simulation software is used to predict the performance ratio, losses in various components and annual energy output of a 50 MW peak grid connected solar PV plant.

2.4.2. About PVsyst

1. One of the oldest software developed by university of Geneva.
2. Main Features
 - Meteorological data analysis
 - Complete database of PV Module, inverter and meteo data
 - Import of solar radiation data from Solar GIS, NASA-SSE and many other databases
 - Create yourself and Import PV Module and solar Inverter data from Photon international
 - Shadow Analysis using 3D models

- Design simulation of Grid connected , Standalone, Solar Pump, DC Grid
- Economic Evaluation
- Probabilistic approach
- Export the data into .CSV and convert into PDF

2.4.3. Information required for PVsyst design

Location Details

1. Co-ordinates: Latitude (N or S) and Longitude (E or W)
2. Pin code State and country

Technical details

1. Type of system :On grid or Off grid
2. PV Module technology: Mono/Poly/Thin-film
3. Module Capacity : W_p (Output wattage) or make
4. Inverter: Type, Capacity and make

Geographical site details

- Check location on google earth :Latitude (N or S) and Longitude (E or W)
- Azimuth angle ($^{\circ}$) : South reference (+ Angle for clockwise, - Angle for anti-clockwise)
- The coordinates of the site or address are entered to access the meteo data which includes Global Irradiance, Diffuse Irradiance, and temperature and wind velocity of the respective geographical location.

Meteo Data

- Irradiation, temperature and wind speed data fetched from various Meteorological database i.e. NASA SE, Meteonorm, and Solar GIS. etc.

2.4.4 PVsyst design procedure

General

- Choose project design option from main menu
- Select new Project > Go to parameter and click on site and meteo data to import the meteo file.

Input Parameters: Mandatory

- Under this section we compute orientation i.e. optimum tilt of module for collecting maximum radiation ,pitch to limit the shading losses
- System : Project capacity (kWp) or Area (Given by the client), Selection of PV Module(Wp) and make, Inverter rating and make, Series and no of strings combination

- Detailed losses: Thermal parameters of NOCT, Ohmic losses, Module quality -LID-Mismatch, Soiling losses, Auxiliaries, Unavailability.

Orientation

Note: Optimum Plane tilt selection with respect to yearly meteo yield and patch selection is done so as to limit the shading losses

1. Choosing the Optimum tilt

- Select the field type if it is based on fixed or select the appropriate tracker used
- The site uses a seasonal tilt tracker, i.e. fixed mounting with manual tilt modification on a seasonal basis
- Input the various tilt angles for the different seasons to get maximum irradiation

2. Pitch selection w.r.t tilt angle to limit the shading losses

- Pitch is the minimum distance b/n two modules to avoid any effect of shadowing under all weather conditions and sun positions throughout the day.
- The value of pitch should be chosen properly to avoid shading losses.
- The global and near shading losses should be within 1.5%

3. Module placement on tilted plane

- Column Bandwidth selection
- If Module mounting is portrait : Enter the length in meters
- If Module mounting is landscape :Enter the width in meters

4. System Module Selection

- Enter the planned power (kWp) or Available area(in q meter)
- Select the PV Module > Selection based on the available ones based on power (Wp) or based on make you can choose from parents offered by different companies and selection based on the type (mono,poly,GaAs).

5. Inverter Selection

- Pre-decide the type of inverter i.e. string,ease of installation and efficiency, No of Mppt,make ,% loading on inverter (oversized or undersized)
- Inverter Should be selected in such a way that Underloading and overloading (DC to AC) ratio must be in acceptable range

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Figure 3: PVsyst system design configuration

2.4.5. Parameters considered for PV plant performance analysis

1. Array yield

It is equal to the time which the PV plant has to operate with nominal solar generator power P_0 to generate array DC energy E_A . Its units are $\text{kW h/d} \cdot \text{kW p}$.

$$Y_A = E_A / P_0$$

where, Array energy output per day $E_A = I_{dc} \cdot V_{dc} \cdot t$ (kW h),

I_{dc} = DC current (A)

V_{dc} = DC voltage (V)

P_0 = Nominal Power at STC.

2. Reference yield

The reference yield is the total in-plane irradiance H divided by the PV's reference irradiance G . It represents the under ideal conditions obtainable energy. If G equals 1kW/m^2 , then Y_R is the number of peak sun hours or the solar radiation in units of kW h/m^2 . The Y_R defines the solar radiation resource for the PV system. It is a function of the location, orientation of the PV array, and month-to-month and year-to-year weather variability. Its units are h/d .

$$Y_R = [kWh/m^2]/1kW/m^2.$$

$$Y_R = H_t/G_0$$

Where,

H_t = Total Horizontal irradiance on array plane (Wh/m^2),

G_0 = Global irradiance at STC (W/m^2).

3. Final yield

The final yield is defined as the annual, monthly or daily net AC energy output of the system divided by the peak power of the installed PV array at standard test conditions (STC) of 1000W/m^2 solar irradiance and 25°C cell temperature. Its units are $\text{kW h/d} \cdot \text{kW p}$.

$$Y_F = EP_{V,AC}/P_{\max}G, \text{ at STC.}$$

4. Performance ratio

The performance ratio is the final yield divided by the reference yield. Performance ratio can be defined as comparison of plant output compared to the output of the plant could have achieved by taking into account irradiation, panel temperature, availability of grid, size of the aperture area, nominal power output, temperature correction values.

$$P_R = Y_F/Y_R.$$

5. Capacity utilization factor

It is defined as real output of the plant compared to theoretical maximum output of the plant.

$$CUF = \text{Energy measured (kW h)} / (365 \cdot 24 \cdot \text{installed capacity of the plant}).$$

6. Inverter efficiency

The inverter efficiency appropriately called as conversion efficiency is given by the ratio of AC power generated by the inverter to the DC power generated by the PV array system. The instantaneous inverter efficiency is given by $H_{\text{inv}} = P_{AC}/P_{DC}$.

7. System efficiency

The instantaneous daily system efficiency is given as PV module efficiency multiplied by inverter efficiency.

$$H_{\text{sys},T} = \eta_{PV,T} \cdot \eta_{\text{inv},T}.$$

8. Energy output or energy fed to utility grid

The energy generated by the PV system is the measure of energy across the inverter output terminals for every minute. It is defined as the total daily monitored value of AC power output and the monthly AC energy generated.

9. Specific plant losses

Energy losses occur in various components in a grid connected SPV Power plant under real operating conditions. These losses are evaluated using the monitored data.

10. Array capture losses (L_C): These are of two types.

- Thermal capture loss (L_{CT}): Losses caused by cell temperature higher than 25 °C are called thermal losses. Thermal capture loss (L_{CT}) is the difference between reference field and corrected reference field.
- Miscellaneous capture loss (L_{CM}): Losses that are caused by wiring, string diodes, low irradiance, partial shadowing, mismatching, maximum power tracking errors, limitation through dust, losses generated by energy conduction in the photovoltaic modules

$$L_{CT} = Y_R - Y_{CR}$$

$$L_{CM} = Y_{CR} - Y_A$$

$$L_C = Y_R - Y_A.$$

11. System losses (L_S)

These losses are caused by inverter, conduction and losses of passive circuit elements.

$$L_S = Y_A - Y_F.$$

2.4.6. Simulation Results

After all the required data is entered in the simulation software following is the report obtained which gives overview of the plant design including all the parameters and constraints discussed above to obtain maximum efficiency and limit the losses to the minimum.

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PVSYST V6.68		20/03/18	Page 1/3
Grid-Connected System: Simulation parameters			
Project : New Project			
Geographical Site	Mekalacheruvu	Country	India
Situation	Latitude 14.08° N	Longitude	78.31° E
Time defined as	Legal Time Time zone UT+5.5	Altitude	529 m
	Albedo 0.20		
Meteo data:	Mekalacheruvu	Meteonorm 7.1 (1981-2010), Sat=100% - Synthetic	
Simulation variant : New simulation variant1			
	Simulation date	20/03/18 10h17	
Simulation parameters	System type	Sheds system, seasonal tilt	
Coll. plane: Seasonal tilt adjustment	Azimuth 0°	Winter season	O-N-D-J-F
	Summer Tilt 3°	Winter Tilt	27°
Models used	Transposition Perez	Diffuse	Perez, Meteonorm
Horizon	Free Horizon		
Near Shadings	No Shadings		
PV Array Characteristics			
PV module	Si-poly	Model	JAP6(BK) 60-240/3BB
Original PVsyst database	Manufacturer	JA Solar	
Number of PV modules	In series	In parallel	8881 strings
Total number of PV modules	Nb. modules 208344	Unit Nom. Power	240 Wp
Array global power	Nominal (STC) 50003 kWp	At operating cond.	44938 kWp (50°C)
Array operating characteristics (50°C)	U mpp 640 V	I mpp	70258 A
Total area	Module area 340674 m²	Cell area	304216 m²
Inverter			
Original PVsyst database	Model	PVS800-57-1000kW-C	
Characteristics	Manufacturer	ABB	
	Operating Voltage 600-850 V	Unit Nom. Power	1000 kWac
		Max. power (=>25°C)	1200 kWac
Inverter pack	Nb. of inverters 50 units	Total Power	50000 kWac
PV Array loss factors			
Thermal Loss factor	Uc (const) 20.0 W/m²K	Uv (wind)	0.0 W/m²K / m/s
Wiring Ohmic Loss	Global array res. 0.15 mOhm	Loss Fraction	1.5 % at STC
Module Quality Loss		Loss Fraction	-0.8 %
Module Mismatch Losses		Loss Fraction	1.0 % at MPP
Strings Mismatch loss		Loss Fraction	0.10 %
Incidence effect, ASHRAE parametrization	IAM = 1 - bo (1/cos i - 1)	bo Param.	0.05
User's needs :	Unlimited load (grid)		
Auxiliaries loss	Proportionnal to Power	4.0 W/kW ... from Power thresh.	0.0 kW

Figure 4: PVSyst simulation parameters

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Figure 5: System Simulation results (PVSyst)

Figure 6: Pvsyst Report and Water Flow diagram

2.4.7. Balances and main results

Annual global horizontal irradiation is 1918.6 kW h/m². Global incident energy that is incident on the collector plane annually is 2088.3 kW h/m². Total energy obtained from the output of the PV array is 16 532 kW h. Annual Efficient E_{out} array/rough area obtained is 10.43%. In the same way annual Efficient E_{out} system/rough area is 10.12%.

2.4.8. Performance ratio

The annual average performance ratio is 80.80%. From PVsyst results the performance ratio obtained has no much difference with the actual performance ratio of the solar plant observed using SCADA system.

2.4.9. Loss diagram

The global horizontal irradiance is 1940 kW h/m². The effective irradiation on the collector plane is 2030 kW h/m². Therefore, the loss in energy is 3.2%. The solar energy incident on the solar panels will convert into electrical energy. After the PV conversion, the nominal array energy is 20 489 MW h. The efficiency of the PV array is 13.30% at standard test condition (STC). Array virtual energy obtained is 16 532 MW h. After the inverter losses the available energy obtained at the inverter output is 16 047 MW h.

2.5. Calculation of Temperature corrected Performance Ratio

2.5.1 Performance Ratio

The Performance Ratio (PR) is the ratio of the actual and theoretical energy outputs. It is represented as a percentage and shows the actual energy available for export to the grid after deducting the auxiliary consumption and losses occurring in the system at various levels. It is the measure of the quality of the PV plant and hence also called quality factor.

PR is largely independent of the orientation of a PV plant and the incident solar irradiation on the PV plant. PR gives the information about energy efficiency and reliability of the solar PV plant. This helps in monitoring the status of the plant over a period of time. It is to be noted that practically a value of 100 % for PR cannot be achieved, as unavoidable losses always arise with the operation of the PV plant. The PR for optimally performing PV plants range between 75%-80%. It is given by the formula:

$$\text{Performance Ratio} = \frac{\text{NetExport}(KWh)}{\text{Total insolation}(KWh/m^2) * \text{Plant capacity}(KW)}$$

Equation 1

2.5.2 Factors effecting Performance Ratio:

1) ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

a) Temperature of the PV module

Efficiency and performance of a solar PV module depends on the temperature of the PV module. It is observed that at lower temperatures, a PV module is more efficient than the PV module at higher temperatures.

Figure 7: Variation of PR with module temperature

The above graph indicates the variation of PR with module temperature for a span of 10 days in the month of January 2018 (winter month). It is observed that the performance ratio is quiet high i.e. in the range of 75%-77% as the module temperature is below 27°C.

Figure 8: Variation of PR with Module temperature(over a year)

Similarly the above graph indicates the variation of PR with module temperature over a year.

It is observed that in summer months (April-June) as the module temperature rises to values up to 40°C and sometimes beyond that, the performance ratio drops down whereas in monsoon and winter months as the temperature drops down below 30°C the performance ratio significantly increases.

b) Solar irradiation

When the sun is low in the sky, the value for the incident solar irradiation approaches that of power dissipation (which is given as the difference between power input and output) more closely than at other times of day/year. Hence PR value is lower than usual at these times.

Figure 9: Variation of PR with solar irradiance (span of 10 days)

The above graph shows the variation of PR with solar irradiance over a span of 10 days. No significant conclusion can be drawn as there is no set pattern observed.

Figure 10: Variation of PR with solar irradiance (over a year)

The above graph shows the variation of PR with solar irradiance over a year. It is observed that during the monsoon and winter months as the average solar irradiance drops the performance ratio also drops indicating a slightly linear relationship.

c) Shading/Soiling of measuring gage

Plants and buildings can throw shadows on PV plant's measuring gage, causing it to be temporarily or even permanently in the shade. When the sun is low, parts of the PV plant itself can cast shadows over the measuring gage. The partial or complete placing in shadow of the measuring gage can result in drop of PR values.

d) Shading/Soiling PV module

Soiling due to bird droppings, dust, pollen, snow etc. can lead to shading of the PV modules which causes lower absorption of solar irradiation than usual. This results in drop of the overall efficiency and PR values of the PV plant.

2) NON ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

a) Recording period

Low solar elevations, low and high temperatures and shading influence the calculation result strongly, as these values may not be completely recorded for a shorter recording period. If the recording period is too short (i.e. less than 1 month), there are insufficient measurements for reliable calculation of PR.

b) Conduction losses

Conduction losses occur in the cable depending on the type and material of cable used during the transmission of energy from the inverter to the energy export meter of the grid operator. This results in the reduction of PR values.

c) Efficiency factor of the PV modules

The efficiency factor of the PV modules influences the PR of PV plant. The higher the efficiency of the PV modules, the higher the PR value with corresponding ambient conditions.

d) Efficiency factor of the inverter

With higher efficiency of the inverter, the PR value increases.

e) Degradation of solar cells

The ageing of the solar cells results in a lower PR value over time. Monocrystalline solar cells and polycrystalline solar cells degrade up to 20 % in 20 years.

2.5.3 Temperature corrected Performance Ratio:

Weather affects the PR by affecting the module temperature depending upon the location on globe. The PR cannot be used to compare PV plants installed in geographical areas due to the large impact on PV cell temperature. So it is desirable to use the temperature corrected PR. Temperature corrected PR enables better forecast of performance of the system in consideration.

FORMULA:

$$\text{Temperature corrected PR} = \text{PR} * \text{Temperature correction factor}$$

Equation 2

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Where: $Temperature\ correction\ factor = \frac{1}{1-\delta*(T_{expected}-T_{measured})}$

Equation 3

T expected: expected average module temperature from pvsyst (°C)

T measured: measured average module temperature (°C)

δ: temperature coefficient of module (%/°C)

The analysis of data obtained from the site is carried out and temperature corrected PR is calculated for a span of 10 days (January 2018) and for a year (2016-2017).

Site details	Capacity in kW
P1 Block	50000

10 DAY ANALYSIS:

DATE	TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT OF MODULE	EXPECTED AVERAGE MODULE TEMPERATURE FROM PVSYST (°C)	MEASURED AVERAGE MODULE TEMPERATURE (°C)	TEMPERATURE CORRECTION FACTOR	PV SYST PR	PR (WITHOUT TEMPERATURE CORRECTION) (%)	TEMPERATURE CORRECTED PR (%)
05-01-2018	-0.41	19.32	25.73	1.026990333	77.93%	74.07%	76.07%
06-01-2018	-0.41	20.27	25.10	1.020203082	77.78%	73.58%	75.07%
07-01-2018	-0.41	20.05	25.12	1.021228272	77.78%	73.89%	75.46%
08-01-2018	-0.41	18.41	24.45	1.025392828	78.37%	75.14%	77.05%
09-01-2018	-0.41	18.85	25.66	1.028722974	78.38%	72.84%	74.93%
10-01-2018	-0.41	20.499	26.90	1.026951416	77.59%	74.01%	76.01%
11-01-2018	-0.41	18.8	28.93	1.043332739	77.97%	73.75%	76.94%
12-01-2018	-0.41	18.98	29.81	1.04646624	78.49%	73.55%	76.97%
13-01-2018	-0.41	17.91	29.14	1.048265278	78.72%	73.25%	76.78%
14-01-2018	-0.41	20.28	27.50	1.030505009	77.49%	74.09%	76.35%
15-01-2018	-0.41	19.01	28.05	1.038490616	78.03%	73.79%	76.63%
16-01-2018	-0.41	19.075	27.43	1.035470562	78.04%	74.37%	77.00%
17-01-2018	-0.41	20.38	26.73	1.02673094	77.38%	74.08%	76.06%

Table 9: 10 Day PR Analysis

Figure 11: Comparison between PR with and without temperature correction (10 days)

The above graph shows a comparison between PR with and without temperature correction over a span of 10 days. Here it can be observed that the temperature corrected PR values are higher than the normally calculated PR values as the temperature correction factor is taken into consideration.

ANALYSIS FOR A YEAR:

A similar exercise is carried for an entire year and the temperature corrected PR values are calculated.

Figure 12: Comparison between PR with and without temperature correction (over a year)

The above graph shows a comparison between PR with and without temperature correction over a year. It is evident that the temperature corrected PR values are higher than the original values.

The temperature correction helps in better estimation of costs and investments. This also helps in more accurate forecast and prediction. Temperature corrected PR gives practical and real time data.

2.6. PV Plant Loss calculations using SCADA and site data

2.6.1 Introduction

Loss calculations for inverter and cable losses are to be calculated on a real-time basis based on SCADA data and other site details.

This data is further compared to PVsyst loss analysis data obtained from the simulated design of the PV system. The accuracy and design of the PVsyst model used to simulate improvements is improved as a result.

Calculations are also done to account for real-time losses or losses that cannot be modelled in a PVsyst simulation, such as

- Cable losses for each inverter unit based on its distance from the PV array field
- Inverter room based loss analysis
- Worst and best performing Inverter rooms
- Dynamic near shading partial losses due to vegetative growth

2.6.2. Cable Losses

General procedure followed for Cable selection in a PV System

Work on optimizing PV Plants and consequently the majority of current research has been mainly focused on the techniques and methodology on improving the efficiency of the solar cells, maximizing the PV output through Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) and inverter topologies. Not much research has been done on cable design and selecting an optimum value based on losses over the lifetime of the PV system.

PV system design practice, for DC Cable selection is usually decided by two constraints

- Satisfying the voltage drop constraint.
- Satisfying thermal constraints.

Joule Losses, or resistive heating losses over the technical lifetime of the cable are usually not taken into consideration.

This practice follows current PV design standards as it is able to guarantee safe PV plant operation, however it isn't an optimal method. PV system analysis rarely takes optimal DC Cable selection into consideration and may lead to an inefficient PV system installation [1].

Voltage drop constraint:

According to the National Electric Code (NEC), the requirements are deemed to be satisfied for a supply given if the voltage drop between the origin of the installation (usually the supply terminal) and the fixed current-using equipment does not exceed 5 percent of the normal voltage of the supply. [2]

Voltage drop should be maintained at less than 5% of voltage supply overall.

According to NEC norms, the overall voltage drop between the PV array and solar inverter must be less than 3%. Voltage drop losses on the ac side should be less than 1.5%

Conclusion

The general limit for cable losses in a well-designed PV system installation should be around 1.5%-2%, which should also remain stable over time.

Future Cable Design should be based on optimal cable loss calculation considering thermal loss build up in the system over time

Procedure followed for DC Cable Loss calculation

- The SMB data from PV arrays for a given day was observed. The output DC power transmitted to each inverter for an inverter room was calculated.
- Inverter room data for a given day was also observed and the input DC power to the inverter was summed.
- The total loss in power from PV array and inverter was calculated for a day and was taken as the DC cable loss for each cable used.
- The cable losses for cables to different inverters were compared and total DC cable losses in the PV System in the system was calculated and conclusions drawn.

DC Cable loss for a single cable

Figure 13: DC Cable losses over a day for a single cable

Observations

- A maximum of 35 KW is lost as Cable loss

DC Cable losses for a single unit

Figure 14: Total DC cable losses to an inverter room

Observations

- The cable losses are minimum during early morning hours when the sunshine falling on panels is less. SMB current and consequently I^2R losses is less. (7:00 AM-11:00 AM)
- Cable losses peak during afternoon hours where sunshine on panel is greater. (11:15 AM-15:15 PM)

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- Cable Losses reduce during later periods (15:30-17:00 PM) and show a sharper decline as sunshine hours end (17:15 PM-18:15 PM)
- DC cable losses from SMB boxes to inverters A, B, C and D of IR-204 is similar.
- This shows that each inverter room has been placed at an equivalent distance from the multiple SMBs connected through cables.

Cable Losses calculated over a day

Note: There are 13 Inverter Rooms, with 50 inverters totally.

Cable Losses at each inverter

Inverter Rooms	A (KW)	B (KW)	C (KW)	D (KW)
201	774.83	779.29	890.84	997.43
202	855.83	939.64	1022.5	1078.5
203	852.6	920.14	840.44	1120.4
204	855.93	946.54	1124.21	1088.56
205	953.64	985.74	876.85	986.54
206	956.68	970.85	998.98	876.97
207	965.46	980.45	789.98	785.88
208	755.73	864.84	859.65	967.34
209	975.68	944.69	924.55	965.6
210	974.34	856.72	924.56	658.59
211	795.57	924.92	957.45	795.84
212	953.34	953.38	1005.63	980.45
213	856.55	835.92	-	-

Figure 15: Cable Losses at each inverter

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Average cable loss per room for operating hours of the plant (7:00 AM to 6:45 PM)

Note: 15 minute time intervals

Inverter Rooms	Average Cable Loss per Room (KW)
201	71.71646
202	81.17646
203	77.78292
204	83.65083
205	79.22438
206	79.23917
207	73.37021
208	71.82417
209	79.38583
210	71.12938
211	72.37042
212	81.1
213	35.25979
Total Cable Loss (KW)	957.23

Table 10: Average Cable Loss per Inverter Room (KW)

Observations made

- Plant has been designed so that cable losses are similar across inverter rooms
- The DC Cable Loss is 1.91% of total output.

Results and Conclusions

The average cable loss of the 50 MW PV site during working hours is 957.23 KW and it is 1.91% of the total output.

DC Cable loss percentage lies within acceptable bounds for a well-designed PV System. (<2%)

2.6.2. Inverter Losses

Types of Inverter Losses

The power losses in an inverter consist of switching losses and conduction losses.

Procedure followed:

- Inverter data for a complete day (taken for 1 hour time intervals) was considered.
- The difference between DC power input to the inverter and its AC output were obtained.
- This was taken as the losses in the inverter, lost as switching losses as well as conduction losses.
- The cumulative losses of all inverters in the PV system throughout the day was calculated and compared with PVsyst simulated inverter loss values for the same date and time period.
- An average of the losses in each inverter room during plant working hours was also obtained (7:00 AM to 6:00 PM)

Variation of Inverter Losses with Inverter temperature

Figure 16: Variation of Inverter Losses with Inverter temperature

As with all semiconductor devices failures due to electrical and thermal stress are the biggest risk. Temperature plays a vital role in analysing such failures [3]

Observations made

- Inverter losses are noted to be higher when inverter temperatures are high.

Average inverter losses for each inverter

Figure 17: Average inverter losses for each inverter

- A comparative loss analysis between different inverters in the PV plant is done
- Using calculated data, the worst performing inverter and inverter room as well as the best performing inverter and inverter room were obtained.

Conclusions drawn

The worst performing inverter room was IR-201, and IR-207 was the best performing inverter room. The worst performing inverter was IR 211-B with an average of 29.2 KW power lost daily, and the best performing inverter was IR 207-C.

The same observations were conveyed on a subsequent site visit.

Comparative analysis of cumulative inverter losses over plant working hours

Figure 18: Comparative analysis of cumulative inverter losses over plant working hours

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Time	Losses	
	From PVsyst	From Data
(1/31/2018)		
5:00	0	0
6:00	0	0
7:00	216.546	22.4
8:00	285.612	149.9
9:00	401.786	338.4
10:00	504.418	471.6
11:00	528.084	506.1
12:00	528.678	551.4
13:00	488.428	584.6
14:00	426.918	522.2
15:00	316.212	435.9
16:00	223.954	307.2
17:00	193.567	141.2
18:00	0	9.7
19:00	0	0
20:00	0	0
Total loss in KW	389.7657	400.85

Table 11: Comparative analysis of cumulative inverter losses over plant working hours

- Data obtained from PVsyst simulation was plotted and compared with that of plant data for the same date.
- Slight deviations can be noted in the overall distribution of inverter loss, as the year used for PVsyst simulation is different from given plant data. There is also a variation due to different sunshine hours experienced over the years.
- This deviation can also be attributed to plant data variations due to dynamic factors such as cloud cover, rainfall or shading losses due to grass growth, affecting sunlight falling on the panel, which is not considered in the meteorological data given in PVsyst.
- However, overall the general inverter loss trend is similar.

Conclusion

- The average daily cumulative inverter loss using PVsyst simulation is 389.76 KW, and using plant data is 400.85 KW.
- From PVsyst simulated data inverter efficiency shows low values during the first working hour as well as the last working (evening) hour, (88-90%>) and is 97-99% efficient otherwise
- Inverter loss percentage is around 0.8% of total output.

2.7. PVsyst simulation Results and discussion

2.7.1. Performance comparison

The results obtained from the monitored SCADA data system is compared with PVSYSY Software. The actual performance closely matches with the simulated performance of PVsyst over the entire year.

A performance study of 50 MW peak grid connected solar photovoltaic power plant installed was evaluated on annual basis. The following conclusions are drawn from the study.

- Maximum total energy generation of 8095 MW h was observed in the month of March and lowest total energy generation of 5941 MW h was observed in the month of August.
- As far as the comparison of monitored data with PVsyst simulation results, plant is operating nearer to the predicted generation of energy modeling software.
- 50 MW solar power plant has been operating with good amount of PR and CUF. The plant has been in operation and feeding energy to grid at an available percentage of almost 99%.

The study provides an insight to identify the location and suitable PV technology for large scale deployment of solar photovoltaic system in India. This information is useful in evaluating the operational benefits of the plant based on the net energy output

2.7.2. Solar irradiance vs. peak power output

Solar irradiance absorbed by solar modules is converted to useful power. The power output varies with the solar insolation and an ambient temperature.[12]

As, the temperature increases the power output decreases up to some extent even if there is good amount of irradiation. Also, with increase in temperature, the power generation decreases slightly even when there is constant solar irradiance.

2.7.3. Variations in energy export vs. consumption on different days

Some amount of power generated from the plant is consumed for its internal power utilities referred to as auxiliary consumption. The power output varies accordingly as radiation varies but the consumption either day or night almost remains constant as there is no change in load of the solar plant. The difference in energy export and consumption should be high. The day's power consumed by the solar plant load is about 200 to 250 kW h and correspondingly its night power consumption is about 1000 kW h. By using the net metering concept power consumed is calculated by the internal utilities and power export to the grid.

The consumption also varies depending on the sun's irradiation. Due to rain or less insolation the solar plant may stop generating power. To analyse these conditions, the plant records auxiliary consumption during day and night.

2.7.4. Performance Ratio (PR)

The annual average value of PR ratio is nearly 80.80%. The highest value of PR is found to be 82.5% in the month of July and the lowest PR was 78.7% in the month of March. System malfunction can be deducted based on the PR values. Lower PR is attributed to the incorrect operation of the system and inverter malfunction.

2.7.5. Energy generation

The data is collected manually by using SCADA software. The highest monthly sum of energy generation was 7875 MW h in the month of March and the lowest was 5000 MW h in the month of November. This is all because of the seasonal tilt of the solar panels and the amount of solar radiation that is absorbed from the sun. The total annually generated output was 81229 MWh.

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MONTH	GUARANTEED GENERATION DETAILS		FINAL GENERATION DETAILS	
	GLOBAL AVERAGE RADIATION ON HORIZONTAL SURFACE (kWh/m2/Day)	GUARANTEED GENERATION IN MILLION UNIT (MU)	RECEIVED GLOBAL AVERAGE RADIATION ON HORIZONTAL SURFACE (kWh/m2/Day)	ACTUAL NET GENERATION IN MILLION UNIT (MU)
JANUARY	166.7	7.546	217.8	7.6057208
FEBRUARY	176.1	7.408	266.33	7.8691315
MARCH	208.3	7.669	276.97	7.8752001
APRIL	201.6	7.264	271.54	7.2997667
MAY	199.4	7.211	272.04	7.6785675
JUNE	159.8	5.886	235.28	6.5659475
JULY	154.8	5.747	208.19	6.1193534
AUGUST	157	5.941	207.18	6.0577172
SEPTEMBER	159.1	6.012	218.13	6.2700110
OCTOBER	143.6	5.639	206.09	6.1770201
NOVEMBER	144.7	6.385	171.59	5.0004411
DECEMBER	145.1	6.698	201.73	6.7105604

Table 12: Comparison between guaranteed generation and actual net generation for a year

Figure 19: Comparison between guaranteed generation and actual net generation for a year

2.7.6. Identification of areas for Performance Optimization

The majority of Losses occurring at the site and which are also viable areas for plant optimization are:

- Seasonal tilt of the PV array field.
- Water losses from PV panel cleaning.
- Partial Shading losses due to grass growth
- Automation of lighting circuit at the plant

2.7.7. Seasonal tilt of the PV array field.

From analysis of plant performance over the year based on the tilt angles of the PV panels used, suggestions of additional tilt angles became a possibility.

2.7.8. Water losses from PV panel cleaning

Large volumes of water are lost in the cleaning of PV panels, as observed from site visits. There are possibilities of minimizing the quantity of water used by improving the cleaning system efficiency and thereby improving the plant's operational efficiency.

2.7.9. Auxiliary Loss and Fuel cost reduction

The energy consumption in the lighting circuits used in the Plant's inverter rooms and control rooms can be reduced, thereby decreasing auxiliary losses and fuel cost involved in manually switching off power supply to each unit in the power plant.

2.7.10. Partial Shading losses due to grass growth

Losses not accounted for in the simulation include partial shading losses due to grass growth around the panel. This is because grass growth is dynamic factor which cannot be modelled in PVsyst simulations or manually calculated on a constant basis. Solutions for reduction of grass growth can be proposed.

These will all be explored in detail in the next chapter

CHAPTER: 3 - IMPROVEMENTS

3.1 IMPROVEMENT 1: PV Panel cleaning using a Mist nozzle system

3.1.1 INTRODUCTION

The performance of PV system can be affected by the accumulation of dirt on solar panels in regions where rainfall is limited for a dry season. This effect is magnified where rainfall is absent in the peak-solar summer months.

The objective of the proposal is to minimize the amount of water and electrical energy needed for cleaning of the solar panels in the grid-connected system. A cleaning system has been designed based on water spraying on PV panels using mist nozzles and a 3-D CAD model is developed and flow simulation is performed for the same using SOLIDWORKS software.

3.1.2 THEORY

The plant performance is inferior most of the time because PV modules have not been cleaned properly. If they are cleaned, the water used for cleaning is not of good quality. Dirt and bird excreta are two major factors which affect the module output.

The environmental conditions that the modules are installed in, play an important role in determining the energy output. Degradation in PV system performance in the range of 15% - 65% for time duration varying from 6 days to 8 months in different parts of the world have been reported. This reduces the yield as well as increases the possibility of module level failures due to hot spots, found in unclean modules. To reduce losses due to dust, bird excreta, pollution, particulate matter and salt water, timely cleaning of the modules are required based on specific environmental concern. Manual cleaning of the modules PV array field, especially in large capacity plants takes considerable time and effort, along with large quantities of materials used. Also at many installation sites, water is a scarce resource, and a general minimization of water usage is preferable as well as economical. Performance ratio of a solar power plant depends on cleaning of modules for achieving desired yield.

Keeping these factors in mind, the following precautions must be taken during cleaning of the panel:

1. Module should be cleaned late in the evening or early morning in order to avoid thermal expansion and cracks because of temperature difference between the water and module surface temperature.
2. The water used should not be too hot or too cold, lukewarm water should be used.

3. The water used should be free from dirt and should be de-mineralized to avoid salt precipitation on module surface. Salty water may also lead to corrosion on module frame as well as the mounting structures.
4. Reverse osmosis (RO) plant can be established to filter the water for cleaning. RO system with a reservoir can be installed in the plant where reservoir will assure, that cleaning cycle of the plant will continue and this will further improve the system yield.
5. Many times the module cleaning is done by water spray jets. The pressure of water spray should not be very high in order to avoid damage on the glass surface due to high pressure of water.
6. Many times it may also require using a soft cloth, sponge, micro-fibre cloth to clean the glass surface. Module can be easily cleaned with these type of wipers as they do not harm the module surface.
7. Dirt spots are harmful for the module and are the main reasons for hot spot on module cells which further leads to damage of the complete module. Removal of these dirt marks should be on priority basis. It should be cleaned through a chemical liquid which is bio-degradable in nature in order to avoid contamination of soil beneath the PV module. If any of the cleaning agent is used, the module should be immediately rinsed with plenty of water to remove the chemical agent on the module surface. Acid or alkaline detergents should be avoided for cleaning the PV modules as they may cause corrosion and erosion of the module frame as well as the mounting structure.
8. Leaning or climbing should be avoided as it may cause micro cracks on the PV module.
9. Automatic machines are available for module cleaning and it is a trade-off between the cost of cleaning the PV modules and the energy yield.
10. A proper analysis should be conducted to decide the cleaning cycle of PV modules so that the energy yield can off-set the cost of cleaning.
11. The cleaning wiper used should be non- adhesive and the water should be removed from top to bottom approach.

Typically, a 5 MW solar PV plant improvement in energy yield by one percent generates about 25 lac per year as additional revenue. Hence, it is possible to increase the energy yield in large plant and increase the plant profitability by maintaining proper cleaning strategy and optimum cleaning cycle.

3.1.2.1 Mist nozzle

Dispersal of water droplets into air is characterized as spray or mist formation. A spray is formed by pressurizing water in a nozzle in order to atomize it.

A mist nozzle facilitates dispersion of liquid into a spray. Mist jet uses air pressure to atomize water. These nozzles breakup the fluid into droplets. Nozzles are used for three purposes:

1. To distribute a liquid over an area
2. To increase liquid surface area
3. Create impact force on a solid surface.

Mist nozzles can be categorized based on the energy input used to cause atomization.

Mist nozzles come in many different styles and sizes i.e., automatic, selectable and manually adjustable. All contain an adjustable baffle that, like a thumb placed on the end of a garden hose, keeps their flow rates and stream reaches steady and finely adjustable despite variations in water pressure at the nozzle.

All styles of mist nozzles have a spray pattern adjustment. These nozzles can produce three different types of streams; the straight stream for long reach, the narrow-angle cone, and the wide-angle cone. The pattern will start out as a full or hollow cone from the nozzle orifice and the pattern will lose coherence and form fog or mist. Many hollow and full cone nozzles will eventually form mist if sprayed at sufficient pressures. There are two designs of nozzle that achieve misting deliberately. They are:

1. **Small orifice nozzle:** It operates at high pressure pushing the fluid through a very small opening to break it apart into fog.
2. **Impingement nozzle:** A stream of fluid is smashed into fog by pushing it into a pin directly below the orifice.

The parameters that affect spray nozzle are:

1. Pressure

For a hydraulic nozzle, higher the fluid pressure, smaller is the droplet size and the relationship pressure. Droplet size greatly depends on the design of the nozzle.

2. Spray pattern type

Flat fan spray has sheets of liquid without much atomization while full cone nozzles produces atomization and hollow cone nozzles produce small droplets.

3. Spray angle

Wider the spray angle, smaller the droplet size. Larger spray angles have more space to distribute the droplets and hence shows greater atomization.

4. Nozzle type

The spray nozzle design affects the spray pattern and the level of atomization. Changing nozzle design changes the consistency of spray pattern.

5. Specific gravity of the fluid

For a given pressure, higher the specific gravity, lower the flow rate and hence reduces the mean droplet size. It affects the overall flow rate at the nozzle hence affecting the droplet size. Specific gravity is usually close to 1.

6. Viscosity and surface tension

Fluids with higher viscosity than water have higher mean droplet size for a given flow rate and pressure. Fluids with higher surface tension form larger droplets.

7. Impact and reach of the spray

For cleaning, impact of a spray is an important characteristic and the spray should have sufficient reach to ensure that it hits the target area and gets well distributed. Spray drift can result in the target being missed or reduced effectiveness if sprayed into a gas flow or in windy conditions. Higher the flow rate, greater the impact of the spray and by increased pressure the impact reduces in certain nozzles. By increasing the pressure, water droplets are atomized to finer droplets which has less momentum. Increasing the fluid pressure increases the internal energy of the fluid and this internal fluid energy is used to atomize the fluid.

3.1.2.2 SOLIDWORKS software

It is a 3D design tool used to model electrical and mechanical structures. It is a solid modelling computer-aided engineering computer program that runs on Microsoft Windows. SOLIDWORKS is published by Dassault Systemes. The software is written on Parasolid-Kernel and uses parametric-feature based approach.

SOLIDWORKS Modelling technology

Building a model in a SOLIDWORKS usually starts with a 2D sketch which includes drawing a point, line, arc, circle and conics. Dimensions are added to the drawing to define the size and location of the geometry. Relations are used to define attributes such as tangency, parallelism, perpendicularity and concentricity. The dimensions of the sketch can be controlled independently or by other parameters inside or outside of a sketch.

Drawings can be created by parts or assemblies and views are automatically generated from solid model, notes, dimensions and tolerance can be added to the drawing.

SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation

SOLIDWORKS simulation is Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) that allows us to analyse a wide range of fluid flow problems. Flow in the atomizing nozzle was solved by SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation. A '.fld' file was generated by SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation.

3.1.3 NOZZLE DESIGN

A half inch nozzle pipe made of stainless steel is used along with a collector. The nozzle pipe is fixed at the top of the panel with the orifice directed towards the panel surface and the separation angle between two water jets is between 60 to 120 degrees. A collector is attached at the bottom of the panel. Mist nozzles are fitted into the nozzle holes with the help of threads. The collector pipe used is three inch in diameter and one meter in length. At one end of the collector, one inch diameter hole along with a sieve, to filter the collected water after cleaning the panel. This forms a recirculating closed water loop. The nozzle pipe along with the collector module are detachable and they do not affect the mechanical stability of the mounted PV panels. The pressure of the mist can be adjusted and the flow rate can be controlled. A micro-fibre cloth can be used to scrub off the dirt on the PV panels. The water collected is filtered to separate the dust particles and the filtrate is reused to clean other PV modules.

A model is designed on SolidWorks 3-D software.

Nozzle specification

Nozzle type	Mist nozzle
Length of swirl chamber(L_s) in mm	41.5
Diameter of swirl chamber(D_s) in mm	22
Length of orifice(L_o) in mm	14.5
Diameter of orifice(D_o) in mm	3
Number of inlet slots(n) in mm	2
Swirl chamber convergent angle(α) in deg	30
Inlet slot diameter(D_e)	1

Table 13 : Nozzle specification

Atomization of water

Pressurized water is applied to nozzles for spraying water on the panel by hydraulic spray systems. Air atomizing systems mix air with water to create fine droplets or fogs for humidification and cooling purposes. In order for the atomization to occur properly each type of spray system has specific nozzles and pressure requirements.

Knowing the water requirement is the first step in designing a water atomizing system. The water requirement for humidification system is based on area of the surface to be cleaned.

Nozzles are classified based on gallons per day or gallons per hour. The nozzle should be selected such that it fits the need for water consumption and air pressure is selected to provide the adequate volume needed for atomization. The nozzles are fitted into the tubing provided and a ball valve is included for cutting off water supply for maintenance purposes. The air-line after the compressor includes the following components in order: air filter, pressure regulator, solenoid and switching relay. Switching relay is attached to the humidistat which turns on the system when the humidity is below the desired set point. A T is installed after the solenoid and a ball valve is connected after T for draining and maintenance. The pressure lines connect to the air side of the atomizing nozzles on the upper half of T fitting.

Pipe is mounted into the area where the atomized water is to be applied. The system should have insulation to prevent air leakage. The humidistat is connected to the air solenoid and water is supplied to the nozzles.

Figure 20: Mist Nozzle Model- Front View

Figure 21: Mist Nozzle model- Tilted view

Figure 22: Mist Nozzle model- Side View

SOLIDWORKS flow simulation steps

1. Flow Wizard setup

Figure 23: Mist Nozzle flow simulation procedure- Flow wizard setup

A project is created under this setup where the type of fluid is chosen to be water and the analysis type is set as internal. This creates a mesh around the structure under consideration.

2. Boundary conditions

Figure 24: Mist Nozzle flow simulation procedure- Boundary Conditions set
Boundaries conditions are set indicating the inlet pressure and outlet conditions. Flow rate is set to the desired value.

3. Goal setting

Figure 25: Mist Nozzle flow simulation procedure- Goal Setting

Surface goals are set to at the inlet and outlet of the nozzle to observe the static pressure. Equation goals are obtained to observe the pressure difference between the inlet of the swirl cylinder and the outlet of the orifice exposed to the surrounding environment.

4. Run the simulation

Figure 26: Mist nozzle flow simulation procedure: Run the simulation-1

Figure 27: Mist nozzle flow simulation procedure: Run the simulation-2
Click on Run to run the simulation and to obtain the simulation results.

5. To obtain Flow trajectory and Cut plot

Figure 28: Mist nozzle flow simulation procedure: Flow trajectory-1

Figure 29: Mist nozzle flow simulation procedure: Flow trajectory-2

After the result is loaded, select Flow trajectory to observe the flow of water within the atomizer. Select Cut plot to observe the differential pressure and velocity of the fluid inside the nozzle.

Simulation report

A report is generated by the software displaying the values of the goals set

Goal Name	Unit	Value	Averaged Value	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
GG Av Velocity 1	[m/s]	1.044831918	1.044572542	1.042092729	1.046032114
SG Av Static Pressure 1	[Pa]	7619675.872	7656380.568	7617008.555	7735303.547
SG Av Static Pressure 2	[Pa]	-185619.6709	-192080.0655	-216959.0958	-174137.7227
Equation Goal 1	[Pa]	7805295.543	7848460.634	7804947.656	7952262.642

Table 14: Mist Nozzle flow trajectory simulation results

Iterations: 40; Analysis interval: 20

The static pressure at the inlet of the swirl cylinder is found to be 7619675.872 Pa and the pressure at the outlet of the orifice is found to be -185619.6709 Pa. The average pressure difference between the inlet and the outlet is 7805295.543 Pa which can be observed in Plot: 1 showing the variation of pressure inside the nozzle. The average velocity of the fluid is 1.0448 m/s and the variation of velocity for 40 iterations can be observed in Plot: 2.

Figure 30: Variation of pressure inside the nozzle model

Figure 31: Variation of velocity of the fluid inside the mist nozzle model

3.1.4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

SUGGESTION: RECYCLED WATER SYSTEM USING A TROUGH COLLECTOR, MIST NOZZLE AND MICROFIBER CLOTH DESIGN

1. The nozzle fit into the pipe is placed at the top of the panel with the collector at the bottom of the PV module.
2. A tank filled with water is connected to the nozzle pipe where the water gushes into the nozzle and the atomized water in the form of mist flows over the PV panel.
3. The inlet pressure is maintained at 75-80 bar pressure to obtain a flow rate of 250 ml/min.
4. A microfiber cloth can be used to scrub off the dirt on the panel after moistening the surface of the panel.
5. A small quantity of water along with the particulate matter flows down the panel and is collected in a collector attachment, similar to a half-cut steel pipe clipped on at the bottom.
6. The water collected can filtered to remove dust particles and the filtrated water thus obtained can be used to clean other PV panels.
7. This forms a recirculating closed water loop. The water used can be recycled and used again.

8. There may be periods during the year where multiple layers of dirt or mud is settled on the panel. A brief spray of normal pressurized water using a normal nozzle can be used first to wash off such layers, after which the mist nozzle and microfiber cloth cleaning procedure is followed.

Figure 33: Solidworks model of water collection system at PV panel-1

Figure 32: Solidworks model of water collection system at PV panel-2

3.1.5 RESULT

Total number of panels=199992 panels; Number of panels cleaned per day=13333 panels;

Man power used for cleaning=10; Cost of water= Rs.750 per 10,000 l

Nozzle type	Amount of water used per panel	Amount of water used per day	Cost of cleaning per day (Rs)
Regular nozzle	750 ml	10,000 l	750
Mist nozzle	80 ml	1066.64 l	80

Table 15: Water savings using suggested PV cleaning system

Amount of water saved in one day= 8933.36 l(approximately)

% Water saved = 89.33%

3.1.6 CONCLUSION

A maximum of 8933.36 litres of water can be saved per day by adopting a cleaning technique using only mist nozzle. The water utilized for cleaning will be collected and reused which further reduces wastage of water.

3.2 IMPROVEMENT 2: REDUCTION IN PARTIAL SHADING DUE TO WEED GROWTH

3.2.1 INTRODUCTION

Weed or vegetation management is particularly important, especially for ground-mounted solar systems. Tall weeds or vegetative growth growing around the installation can create shading, which can negatively impact system production. It can also cause hot spot heating as if a part of the solar cell is shaded, the cell can heat up to such extreme temperatures that a module can burn out causing permanent damage. This problem is exacerbated in large PV plants as weed removal for a huge land area of PV arrays is complex. There are difficulties faced in effective weed removal in all areas of the plant; due to time constraints, large surface area, costs in manual labour, difficulty in finding eco-friendly methods as well as continuous regrowth of weeds.

3.2.2 THEORY

3.2.2.1 Partial Shading

The output current of a PV module is a function of solar irradiance. If there is a reduction in solar irradiance as a result of partial or complete shading, the performance of the PV module will be affected. According to statistical studies, power losses due to partial shading can vary from 10% to 70%. [1]

Types of shadings are **near shadings** and **far shadings**. Shadings from objects that act on the PV array field in a global way is known as “far” shadings, such as when the sun is visible or not visible for an instant on the PV panels, and typically occurs when the shading object is more than 10 times the size of the PV field size.

Far shading is generally compensated for in most well designed PV plants. The design of the site is usually such that shading done due to mountains or far away objects are prevented from casting shadows on the PV panel surface area.

Near shading caused due to shadows of the mounted panel structures falling on nearby panels is also generally minimized. However, vegetation growth consisting of wild grass and other weeds is difficult to prevent. This is a problem faced frequently in PV plants, especially large scale ones set up near forested or other areas where grass seeds easily enter PV fields due to wind dispersal and other methods of seed propagation.

3.2.2.2 Grass growth

Grass growth covers a maximum of 10-20% of the lower mounted panel's surface area at any given time. Currently mowing or grass cutting is being undertaken as a measure for partial shading reduction. Mowing is very labour-intensive and needs to be repeated on a bi-monthly basis for the given site area, and commonly among PV plants of similar power outputs. Besides hiring people or renting mowing equipment, there are fees for hauling and disposing the grass clippings.

3.2.2.3 Site specific details

1. Grass cutting is done for PV panel arrays connected to a single inverter room on a bimonthly basis. This process is repeated in a serial basis
2. The PV array field does not have levelled land and therefore completely automated grass cutting machines cannot be used
3. Herbicide usage that can modify the surrounding habitat or can cause health problems cannot be used according to land usage rights set by the government.
4. The site must maintain environmental standards set by the government, and as part of its balance of systems, is kept operational in a way such that operational and maintenance activities at the plant does not disturb the ecological balance of the surrounding area.
5. Methods to reduce grass growth over time such as the use of rubber sheets or landscape sheets cannot be used in such large plant areas
6. Usage of herbivorous animals like cows or sheep is not used due to potential chances of electrocution as well as non-reliability for larger plant areas.

3.2.2.4 Simulink

Simulink is a block diagram environment that facilitates multidimensional simulation

3.2.3 SIMULATION OF PARTIAL SHADING LOSS FOR A PANEL BASED ANALYSIS:

3.2.3.1 COMPONENTS USED

1. A Tata Solar TP250MZ PV Panel is used.
2. The system consists of a string containing 2 sets of 24 panels connected in series which is then connected parallel to each other.
3. DC Voltage and DC Current measurement blocks are used to measure current (I_{mpp}) and voltage (V_{mpp}) parameters of the total arrangement

4. Ramp irradiation and Temperature input blocks to PV array
5. Relevant scope blocks are connected to measure output current and voltage from each block.

3.2.3.2 SIMULINK DESIGN

1. Due to the dynamic nature of grass growth along with the overall shape of the near shading, which may or may not cover only a corner, containing or not containing the bypass diodes in the panel, modelling is highly complicated.
2. Thus only the partial shading falling on one array string is simulated and the general range of partial losses are noted.
3. The 48 panel arrangement is split into 6 blocks of 8 cells each. The 6 blocks are connected with 3 blocks in series connected in parallel to another 3 blocks in series, i.e., modelled as 6 modules with 8 cells each.
4. The lower blocks are susceptible to partial shading due to vegetation.
5. Partial shading can be simulated by showing the corresponding reduction in irradiance received on panel surface due to grass cover.
6. The pattern of partial shading can vary in shape and size throughout the year. The shaded area can cover the bypass diodes or not according to which output V-I and P-V curves vary.
7. According to general trends noted from the site, a maximum of 5%-20% of panel area is covered, and a minimum of 0%-5% of panel area covered is possible at any given time during the year.
8. From grass cutting reports on site, an improvement of anywhere up to a peak of 15A-16A in PV string output is noted after grass cutting during afternoon hours.

3.2.3.3 ASSUMPTIONS MADE IN DESIGN

1. Upper line of string is not affected by grass growth and resultant near shading.
2. Irradiance at upper line of string is taken as 1000 W/m^2
3. A comparison is made of output at MPP when temperature parameter is not considered as well as when average temperature during peak sunshine hours (11 A.M-2 P.M) is taken.
4. The average peak temperature is taken as 35° for the purpose of this analysis.
5. Partial shading patterns are taken assuming various grass growth locations and heights. Irradiance received at each block is always taken at a minimum of 200 W/m^2 considering the safe working of panel and other factors such as grass cutting periods.

3.2.3.4 SIMULINK RESULTS:

Figure 34: Simulink model under normal conditions and peak irradiance to all cells

Figure 35: V-I and P-V curves of string at peak irradiance to all cells (Temperature losses not considered)

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Figure 36: V-I and P-V characteristics at 35°C and peak irradiance

Figure 37: PV Block current when no partial shading occurs

Figure 38: All block currents and voltages when no partial shading occurs

3.2.4 RESULTS OBTAINED THROUGH SIMULATION:

The MPP power when peak irradiance (taken as 1000 W/m^2) is received at the cell is 11950 W at when temperature parameter is not considered and 11450 W when peak temperature of 35°C is considered.

Simulink Model under partial shading of String (48 cells)

Figure 39: Partial shading simulation for PV string due to grass cover

Figure 40: PV Current from individual blocks due to partial shading at two blocks

Figure 41: Output current and voltage from all blocks during partial shading of two blocks

3.2.4.1 Case 1: Minimum partial shading loss (5%)

Here, for an minimum of 5% of panel covered due to grass growth, the resultant partial shading losses are shown. Partial shading Losses are obtained excluding temperature losses. Partial shading including temperature losses is calculated at an average peak temperature of 35 degrees celsius. A table with power, current and voltage at MPP for multiple possible near shading shapes that cover 5% of the string panel area is shown.

Type of Shading	Lower line of String (24 cells)			At MPP (Temperature not considered)			MPP at 35° C (Considering Temperature)			Losses (W)	
	W /m ² (9-16)	W/m ² (25-32)	W/m ² (41-48)	V _{mpp} (V)	I _{mpp} (A)	P (W)	V _{mpp} (V)	I _{mpp} (A)	P (W)	Excluding L _T (11950 W-Losses)	Including L _T 35degrees (11450 W-Losses)
Equal (with bypass diode)	900	900	900	721	15.78	11380	691	15.82	10940	570	510
Ramp	950	900	850	710.4	15.65	11117	695.4	15.58	10830	833	620
Two blocks (Equal)	1000	850	850	726	15.45	11210	695.1	15.5	10770	740	680
Two blocks	1000	900	800	727.9	15.79	11120	683.3	15.43	10540	830	910
One block (Corner)	1000	1000	700	736	14.2	10450	709.5	14.17	10060	1500	1390

Table 16: Power, current and voltage at MPP for multiple possible near shading shapes that cover 5% of the string panel area

Figure 42: Resultant I-V and P-V characteristic curve for shape with maximum partial shading losses at 5%

Figure 43: Resultant I-V and P-V characteristic curve for shape with minimum partial shading losses at 5%

Results:

Partial shading losses range from 570 W to 1500 W when temperature losses is not considered. Partial losses range from 510 W to 1390 W when temperature losses at 35 degrees is considered.

3.2.4.2 Case 2: Maximum Partial Shading loss (when 20% of PV string is covered)

Here, for an assumed 20% of panel covered at a corner, the resultant partial shading losses are shown. This case is taken as the maximum panel losses due to grass growth if not cut.

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A table with power, current and voltage at MPP for multiple possible near shading shapes that cover 20% of the string panel area is shown.

Partial shading Losses are calculated excluding temperature losses as well as including temperature losses at an average peak temperature of 35 degrees celsius.

Type of Shading	Lower line of String (24 cells)			At MPP (Temperature not considered)			MPP at 35° C (Considering Temperature)			Losses (W)	
	W /m ² (9-16)	W/m ² (25-32)	W/m ² (41-48)	V _{mpp} (V)	I _{mpp} (A)	P (W)	V _{mpp} (V)	I _{mpp} (A)	P (W)	Excluding L _T (11950 W-Losses)	Including L _T 35degrees (11450 W-Losses)
Equal (with bypass diode)	800	800	800	721.6	13.29	9588	690.1	13.35	9212	2362	2238
Ramp	900	750	350	730.7	11.23	8204	702.1	11.23	7893	3746	3557
Two blocks (Equal)	900	450	450	727.2	12.11	8803	698.9	12.1	8456	3147	2994
Two blocks (Unequal)	1000	650	250	728.6	10.38	7286	727.2	12.11	8803	4664	2647
Two blocks (Unequal)	1000	800	200	506.1	15.26	7754	698.9	10.41	7275	4196	4175

Table 17: Power, current and voltage at MPP for multiple possible near shading shapes that cover 20% of the string panel area

Figure 44: Resultant I-V and P-V characteristic curve for shape with maximum partial shading losses when shaded (20%)

Figure 45: Resultant I-V and P-V characteristic curve for maximum partial shading losses when shaded (20%)

Results:

Partial shading losses when a maximum of 20% the PV string is shaded lies between a range of 2362W and 4196 W when temperature losses aren't considered. : Partial shading losses when a maximum of 20% the PV string is shaded lies between a range of 2238W and 4175 W when temperature losses are considered for 35 degrees.

3.2.5 PROPOSAL: ORGANIC CONTACT HERBICIDE AND SALT SPRAYING SYSTEM TO REDUCE VEGETATIVE GROWTH

3.2.5.1 Solution Constraints

1. Site conditions preclude the usage of systemic herbicides as they have a permanent effect on the environment. Any external herbicide used can only be used after multiple studies proving its long term harmlessness on the environment.
2. Contact herbicides that are corrosive in nature or affect surrounding human or animal life on direct or indirect contact can also not be used.
3. The herbicides used must also be relatively inexpensive in nature with respect to auxiliary costs in running mowing equipment or paying for manual labour.

With respect to the constraints acetic acid (Vinegar) and salt mixture can be used along with a fertilizer sprayer to cull vegetative life in and around PV panel arrays.

10% Acetic acid is non-hazardous to plant and animal life, and works by breaking down plant tissue on contact.

Acetic acid and citric acid are alternative materials that work as nonselective, post-emergence, contact herbicides causing rapid desiccation of plant foliage. Their use as herbicides involves application as a foliar spray at concentrations ranging from 10% acetic acid, citric acid, or blends of the two on weeds that are about 6 to 9 inches tall or less. As growth stage advances, control and biomass suppression decreases and survival increases. Generally, 80 to 100% kill rates can be expected for small annual and perennial weeds, but perennial species with persistent root systems will regrow within several months. [1]

Salt application increases sodium levels in the soil due to which plant roots wither due to osmotic pressure increase. The reductions in growth and photosynthesis is greater under NaCl stress and the effect is additive. [2]

3.2.5.1 Procedure

1. Initial grass cutting around a single inverter room is followed by (10%) vinegar spray.
2. Since a contact herbicide deals with break-down of plant tissue at surface level, roots of the grass will remain.
3. Salt is further sprinkled on the same area
4. This creates NaCl stress along with killing the remaining grass roots.
5. Further grass growth in the same area is also drastically reduced.
6. The total time period taken for grass to start to regrow will be several weeks to 3 months.
7. Grass will not thus regrow to a height that will cause partial shading on module as compared to the method using simple grass cutting where at any given time, only a few hundred strings remain unshaded in the huge PV array field.
8. This procedure reduces also overall grass growth over a year's period drastically. Repeated applications cause a cumulative effect and over a period of years, cause further and further decrease in grass growth.
9. An additional precautionary method can be taken by slowly replacing cut grass area with low lying grass species that are drought resistant as well as inexpensive, which will reduce surface area for normal grass to grow.
10. Cost estimates suggest that over a five year period, this methods is as cost effective as single application herbicides, while posing fewer concerns over impacts on human and ecosystem health.[7]

3.2.6 RESULTS

After a year of application of grass removal methods:

Original System

Bimonthly improvement due to grass cutting will only eliminate partial shading losses due to PV strings that go to a single inverter room.

Assuming grass takes 2-3 months to regrow and cause partial shading again under normal methods, due to which only 6-7 Inverter Room PV field arrays remain completely unshaded at any given time. This means a minimum of 2000 out of 4187 strings have various portions of their PV panel shaded in a range of 5%-20%.

The overall partial shading losses at peak irradiance lies between a range of 1140 KW - 8392 KW (excluding losses due to temperature) and 2020 KW - 8350 KW (considering temperature losses at 35 degrees).

Improvement Proposal

Using the suggested improvement, a minimum of 5-6 months will be taken for grass to regrow to original height at cut panel, which means only about 800-1000 strings will be shaded after one year, and the partial shading will further decrease in future years.

The overall partial shading losses at peak irradiance lies between a range of 456 KW and 3356 KW, excluding losses due to temperature and 408 KW to 3340 KW considering temperature losses at 35 degrees.

3.2.7 CONCLUSION:

Array Power improvement in the range of 600 KW - 5036 KW can be seen (excluding temperature losses) at any given time depending on real-time grass growth patterns at site. Considering temperature losses, Array power improvement in the range of 1612 KW - 5010 KW can be similarly obtained using this suggestion.

3.3 IMPROVEMENT 3: AUTOMATED SWITCHING AND LIGHTING CIRCUIT

3.3.1 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The Power Plant is spread widely over 504 acres of land consisting about 26 pre-engineered buildings (PEBs) which have connected lighting and fan circuits along with other auxiliary supply needs. These buildings are placed at a significant distance from each other as well as the main control room. In order to address this issue an IoT based control module was designed and a prototype was developed, based on the layout and existing wiring scheme of the inverter rooms.

3.3.2 OBJECTIVE & PURPOSE

1. The Power Plant is spread widely over 504 acres of land consisting about 26 control rooms which are placed at some significant distance from each other as well as the control room.
2. Using IoT technology we will be automating the control rooms of the power plant for easy and wireless control of appliances used in the control rooms
3. Instead of commuting to the control rooms every time (takes some time) automating the equipment will save some man power and fuel costs(commuting is done using a car in the plant)

3.3.3 THEORY

3.3.3.1 IoT

The internet of things (IoT) is the inter-networking of physical devices, vehicles, buildings and other items—embedded with electronics, software, sensors, actuators, and network connectivity that enable these objects to collect and exchange data.

3.3.3.2 IoT Architecture

The Internet of things (IOT) is a rapid explained technology that is shaping up to bring the next revolution in computing and information technology. IOT system has application across industries through their unique flexible and ability to be suitable in any environment. The physical layer consists of the devices that are to be controlled. The sensors to sense the surrounding environmental conditions are also connected to this layer. The data link layer consists of IoT gateway router (here, we have used NodeMCU as router gateway), device manager and various communication protocols. This layer links the home appliances to the web server or cloud via Wi-Fi communication. The application and presentation layer consist

of web protocol. This layer constitutes either designing of a webpage for accessing the devices connected to the perception layer via PC or laptop computer, or building an android or iOS mobile application if the devices are to be controlled and monitored via smartphones.

3.3.3.3 Blynk

Blynk is a Platform with iOS and Android apps to control various micro-controllers like Arduino, Raspberry Pi and the likes over the Internet. It's a digital dashboard where you can build a graphic interface for your project by simply adding various widgets available on the application. Blynk is not tied to some specific board or shield. Instead, it supports various hardware of your choice. Whether your Arduino or Raspberry Pi is linked to the Internet over Wi-Fi, Ethernet or this new ESP8266 chip, Blynk will get you online and ready for the Internet of Your Things.

3.3.3.4 Blynk Application

Blynk app consists of various widgets which can be added. It can hold and drag them to reposition. Tap once to get to Widget Settings. The main thing you need to set is PIN you want to control (GPIO). A unique authentication token is provided which is to be uploaded to the Node MCU bridging both the hardware and the software. Make to select Node MCU as board in Blynk app. Add on/off buttons and select the appropriate gpio pin.

3.3.3.5 Blynk Server

Blynk Server is an Open-Source Netty based Java server, responsible for forwarding messages between Blynk mobile application and various micro controller boards (i.e. Arduino, Raspberry Pi. Etc.)

3.3.3.6 Arduino IDE

Arduino is an open source computer hardware and software company, project, and user community that designs and manufactures single-board micro controllers and micro controller kits for building digital devices and interactive objects that can sense and control objects in the physical and digital world. The project's products are distributed as open-source hardware and software, which are licensed under the GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL) or the GNU General Public License (GPL), permitting the manufacture of Arduino boards and software distribution by anyone. Arduino boards are available commercially in preassembled form, or as do-it-yourself (DIY) kits. A program for Arduino may be written in any programming language with compilers that produce binary machine code for the target processor. Atmel provides a development environment for their micro controllers, AVR Studio and the newer Atmel Studio. The Arduino project provides the Arduino integrated development

environment (IDE), which is a cross-platform application written in the programming language Java. It originated from the IDE for the languages Processing and Wiring. It includes a code editor with features such as text cutting and pasting, searching and replacing text, automatic indenting, brace matching, and syntax highlighting, and provides simple one-click mechanisms to compile and upload programs to an Arduino board. It also contains a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a hierarchy of operation menus. The Arduino IDE supports the languages C and C++ using special rules of code structuring. The Arduino IDE supplies a software library from the Wiring project, which provides many common input and output procedures.


```
ESP8266_Standalone | Arduino 1.8.0
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
ESP8266_Standalone
* Note: This requires ESP8266 support package:
* https://github.com/esp8266/Arduino
*
* Please be sure to select the right ESP8266 module
* in the Tools -> Board menu!
*
* Change WiFi ssid, pass, and Blynk auth token to run :)
*
-----/
#define BLYNK_PRINT Serial // Comment this out to disable prints and save space
#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#include <BlynkSimpleEsp8266.h>

// You should get Auth Token in the Blynk App.
// Go to the Project Settings (nut icon).
char auth[] = "YourAuthToken";

// Your WiFi credentials.
// Set password to "" for open networks.
char ssid[] = "YourNetworkName";
char pass[] = "YourPassword";

void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(9600);
  Blynk.begin(auth, ssid, pass);
}

void loop()
{
  Blynk.run();
}

Invalid library found in C:\Users\Pruthvi\Documents\Arduino\libraries\breadboard-1-6-x: C:\Users\Pruthvi\Documents\Arduino\libraries\breadboard-1-6-x
NodeMCU 1.0 (ESP-12E Module), 80 MHz, 115200, 4M (M SPIFFS) on COM11
11:02
30-03-2018
```

Figure 46: Arduino code

3.3.3.7 Fritzing

Fritzing is an open-source hardware initiative that makes electronics accessible as a creative material for anyone. We offer a software tool, a community website and services in the spirit of Processing and Arduino, fostering a creative ecosystem that allows users to document their prototypes, share them with others, teach electronics in a classroom, and layout and manufacture professional pcbs.

By using Fritzing we will be designing the layout of our circuit. Some of the parts are available in the bin, but some might not be available but they can be imported from sites like GitHub.

Figure 47: Fritzing layout

3.3.3.8 Node MCU

Figure 48: Node MCU

Node MCU IoT platform node MCU is open source. Language used in it is lua scripting language. It is on the eLua project, and built on the ESP8266 SDK 0.9.5. It uses many open source projects, like lua-cjson, and spiffs. It includes firmware which runs on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi SoC, and hardware on the ESP-12 module. NodeMCU was created shortly after the ESP8266 came out. Espressif systems began production of the ESP8266. The ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi SoC integrated with a Tensilica Xtensa LX106 core, widely used in IoT applications. NodeMCU started in 13 Oct 2014, when Hong committed the first file of NodeMCU - firmware to GitHub. Two months later, the project expanded to include an open-hardware platform when developer Huang R committed the garter file of an ESP8266 board, named devkit 1.0. Later that month, Tuan PM ported MQTT client library from Contiki to the ESP8266 SoC platform, and committed to Node MCU project, then Node MCU was able to support the MQTT IoT protocol, using Lua to access the MQTT IoT protocol, using Lua to access the MQTT broker. Another

important update was made on 30 Jan 2015, when Devsaurus ported the u8glib to NodeMCU project, enabling NodeMCU to easily drive LCD, Screen, OLED, even VGA displays.

It is one of the most stable ESP8266 Boards.

Node MCU Breakout

PIN DEFINITION

D0(GPIO16) can only be used as gpio read/write, no interrupt supported, no pwm/i2c/ow supported.

Figure 49: Node MCU breakout

Operating Voltage	3.3V
Input Voltage (recommended)	5V
Digital I/O Pins	9
PWM Digital I/O Pins	8 (all pins except D0)
Analog Input Pins	1
DC Current per I/O Pin	12 mA
DC Current for 3.3V Pin	50 mA
EEPROM	4 MBytes
Clock Speed	80 MHz

Table 18: Node MCU specifications

3.3.3.9 Buck Converter

A buck converter (step-down converter) is a DC-to-DC power converter which steps down voltage (while stepping up current) from its input (supply) to its output (load). It is a class of switched-mode power supply (SMPS) typically containing at least two semiconductors (a diode and a transistor, buck converters) provide much greater power efficiency as DC-to-DC converters than linear regulators, which are simpler circuits that lower voltages by dissipating power as heat, but do not step up output current.

Buck converters can be highly efficient (often higher than 90%), making them useful for tasks such as converting a computer's main (bulk) supply voltage (often 12 V) down to lower voltages needed by USB, DRAM and the CPU

Figure 50: Buck Boost Converter

3.3.3.10 Relay

We will be using a 12V 4 channel relays each of it has a rating of 10A.

A relay is an electrically operated switch. Relays are used where it is necessary to control a circuit by a separate low-power signal, or where several circuits must be controlled by one signal NC COM NO of Relay

COM - Common connection--> It is the centre terminal and is hot as power to the load is connected at this terminal.

NO Normally open ---> It acts like a switch, since it is open - there will be no contact between COM and NO, When we trigger the relay module, it connects to COM by the electromagnet inside the relay and supply to the load is provided, which powers up the light. Thus the circuit is closed until we trigger the state to low in relay.

NC Normally closed---->It is always in contact with COM, even when relay is not powered. When we trigger the relay it opens the circuit, so the connection is lost. It behaves just opposite to NO.

Circuit symbol for a relay

Figure 51: Circuit symbol for a relay

Figure 52: Relay module

3.3.4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.3.4.1 Components used

1. Node MCU
2. Buck Converter (12V to 3.3V)
3. 4 Channel 12V relay
4. Wires
5. PCB

3.3.4.2 Schematic Diagram

Figure 53: Schematic Diagram of Prototype

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Figure 54: Pin connections of the prototype

Figure 55: PCB Design of the prototype

3.3.4.3 Code

```
#define BLYNK_PRINT Serial // Comment this out to disable prints and save space

#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>

#include <BlynkSimpleEsp8266.h>

char auth[] = "YourAuthToken";

// Your WiFi credentials.

// Set password to "" for open networks.

char ssid[] = "YourNetworkName";

char pass[] = "YourPassword";

void setup()

{

  Serial.begin(9600);

  Blynk.begin(auth, ssid, pass);}

void loop()

{

  Blynk.run();

}
```

3.3.4.4 Prototype Working

Figure 56: Working Prototype model

1. The code is dumped on the NodeMCU and connectivity is checked.
2. The prototype has 2 things the client and the host. The client being the node MCU and the host being the device on which Blynk is installed.
3. The client needs a dedicated WiFi network to work on. The best advantage that blynk offers is the client and the host need not necessarily be on the same network. There by giving us remote access.
4. The relays of the prototype is connected to the appliances via 2 way switch mechanism to have a manual override in case if the prototype is down.
5. The prototype has been tested out for both AC and DC loads. We can observe some delay if the signal strength is less but the delay is minimal

Figure 57: 2-way switch working-1

Figure 58: 2-way switch working-2

Blynk Dashboard

Using Blynk dashboard we can control the GPIO pins which are connected to the relays. The relay outputs are connected to the AC and DC loads which can be controlled using the blynk dashboard. The connections from the relay to the appliances are as follows.

Figure 59: Blynk dashboard view-1 & view-2

3.3.5 WIRING DIAGRAM

AutoCAD, a modelling software is used to obtain wiring diagram as well as 3D layout of inverter rooms where the circuit will be used.

Calculations:

Let the number of load points which can be controlled using the prototype in the control room be as follows:

SLNO.	LOAD TYPE	WATTAGE	LOAD POINTS	TOTAL LOAD
1.	Lighting fixtures	56 W	8	448 W
2.	Exhaust fans	200 W	4	800 W
	Total		12	1248 W

Table 19: Load point calculations

Let supply voltage be considered as 240 V

Number of sub-circuits = 2

(As maximum load in a sub-circuit can be 800 W and the total load present is 1248 W)

Rating of Main Switch Board and Distribution Board:

$$\text{Line current} = \frac{\text{Connected load}}{\text{Supply voltage}}$$

$$\text{Line current} = 1248/240 = 5.2 \text{ A}$$

Therefore line current = 5.2 A

Load in each sub-circuit:

SUB-CIRCUIT 1					SUB-CIRCUIT 2				
SLNO	LOAD TYPE	WATTAGE	LOAD POINTS	TOTAL LOAD	SLNO	LOAD TYPE	WATTAGE	LOAD POINTS	TOTAL LOAD
1.	Lighting Fixtures	56 W	4	224 W	1.	Lighting Fixtures	56 W	4	224 W
2.	Exhaust Fans	200 W	2	400 W	2.	Exhaust Fans	200 W	2	400 W
	Total		6	624 W		Total		6	624 W

Table 20: Total Load in sub-circuit 1

Table 21: Load in sub-circuit 2

Full load current in each sub-circuit = $624/240 = 2.6 \text{ A}$

Therefore full load current in each sub-circuit = 2.6 A

Figure 60: Wiring Diagram for proposed prototype

Figure 61: AutoCAD 3D layout of inverter room

3.3.6 Future Scope

1. This prototype can be expanded for higher rated appliances by changing relays of higher rating.
2. Install it throughout the plant and to get a centralized control over all the appliances throughout the plant basically automate the whole plant.
3. Integrating sensors possibly pyranometers, wind sensors, temperature sensors of the plant and displaying the values on the common dashboard.

3.4 IMPROVEMENT 4: SEASONAL TILT ARRANGEMENT

3.4.1 INTRODUCTION

Earth's elliptical orbit around the Sun, Earth's rotation on its axis, and the tilt of Earth's axis affect the intensity of solar radiation striking the Earth. Due to this the incidence angle of the sunlight also varies resulting in variations in the insolation received at any point on earth throughout the year. In order to maximise the absorption of solar radiation, it is necessary that the panels are tilted at an angle from the horizontal surface such that they are perpendicular to the sun's rays.

3.4.2 THEORY

3.4.2.1 Relation between the tilt angle and solar irradiation:[1]

Standard equations used to determine the relation between tilt angles and received solar radiation on a tilted surface are briefly described below.

First, the solar intensity is calculated using Air Mass, which accounts for the direct optical path length through earth's atmosphere. The simplified formula for Air Mass calculation is:

$$AM = \frac{1}{\cos\Theta}$$

Equation 4

Where, Θ is the angular height of the sun in the sky calculated from the vertical, known as zenith angle. Θ is calculated as follows:

$$\Theta = 90^\circ - \text{elevation angle}$$

Equation 5

Now, the direct component of solar intensity is calculated using the following equation:

$$I = 1.353 * 0.7^{AM^{0.678}}$$

Equation 6

Where, I is the intensity of the sunray on a perpendicular plane and calculated in units of kW/m². To account for the diffuse radiation component, which is nearly 10% of the direct radiation component, the formula for solar intensity is modified as follows:

$$I = 1.1 * 1.353 * 0.7^{AM^{0.678}}$$

Equation 7

Finally, the relation between tilt angles and received solar radiation is established using the following formula

$$\text{Solar Radiation} = I * \sin(\alpha + \beta)$$

Equation 8

Where, β is the tilt angle of the module calculated from the horizontal, and α is the elevation angle which accounts for the angular height of the sun in the sky calculated from the horizontal. Elevation angle is hemisphere dependent. For North hemisphere, the elevation angle is calculated as follows:

$$\alpha = 90^\circ - \text{latitude angle} + \text{declination angle}$$

Equation 9

The declination angle, δ is calculated using the following formula:

$$\delta = 23.45^\circ * \sin\left(\frac{360}{365} * (d - 81)\right)$$

Equation 10

Where, d is the number of a day in a year that starts with January 1 as d = 1.

3.4.2.2 Types of solar panel array mountings:

1. Fixed Mounting:

In fixed mounting arrangement the solar panels always face the equator i.e. true south in northern hemisphere and true north in southern hemisphere. The solar panels are completely stationary and hence there is no scope for tracking the sun

2. Adjustable Mounting

In adjustable mounting arrangement there is a provision on the mounting structure to provide two or more tilts for the panels in order to accommodate the higher angle of sun in summer and lower angle of sun in winters. This helps in improving the overall power output from the panels.

3. Tracker Mechanism

In tracker mechanism a solar tracker is used which orients the solar panels towards the sun. The main types of trackers are Single axis trackers-with one degree of freedom. Dual axis tracker-with two degrees of freedom.

3.4.3 OBSERVATIONS MADE:

In the site location, the existing mounting arrangement is an adjustable mounting arrangement with seasonal tilt. In order to improve the existing system, optimum tilting angles should be identified and operated.

From the analysis of the insolation data obtained from the plant site, it is evident that the plant is receiving very good insolation throughout the year. The current tilt arrangement is a two tilt arrangement system where the panel tilts are changed twice a year i.e. 3° during summer months and 27° during the winter month.

CURRENT TILT ARRANGEMENT				
MONTH	TILT USED	TILT IRRADIATION	ENERGY GENERATED	PERFORMANCE RATIO (%)
		N	Million units(MU)	
		kWh/m².day		
MARCH-SEPTEMBER	3°	5.252618452	35.739749	81.68%
OCTOBER-MARCH	27°	5.98111747	42.349402	82.77%
		5.616867961	78.089151	82.22%

Table 22: Table indicating the performance of the plant with the current tilt arrangement available at the plant

In an attempt to tap more solar energy a suggestion to increase the number of tilt angles is made. The effect of varying the tilt angle on collected monthly solar radiation can be seen in terms of the total output power generated.

3.4.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR OPTIMIZATION:

With the aim of suggesting optimum tilt angles other than the existing tilt arrangement (3° & 27°) an analysis is carried out on the simulated reports generated for various tilt angles ranging from 3° to 27° using PVsyst PC software package. The following suggestions are made.

3.4.4.1 SUGGESTION 1: CHANGING TILT ANGLES MONTHLY

Calculations are done and a table comparing the tilt irradiance received, energy generated and the resultant performance ratio is shown along with the yearly percentage improvement from each parameter. Here, the tilt suggested is changed on a monthly basis: April-August (3°), March (17°), September (13°), October (23°), November-February (27°).

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SUGGESTION 1 : CHANGING TILT ANGLES MONTHLY				
MONTH	TILT SUGGESTED	TILT IRRADIATION	ENERGY GENERATED	PERFORMANCE RATIO (%)
		kWh/m ² .day	Million units(MU)	
JANUARY	27°	6.7120	8.8800	85.60%
FEBRUARY	27°	6.7438	7.9512	84.43%
MARCH	17°	6.7146	8.6419	83.28%
APRIL	3°	6.2208	7.3291	79.05%
MAY	3°	5.8146	7.1988	80.42%
JUNE	3°	4.9878	6.1559	82.74%
JULY	3°	4.6868	6.0142	83.13%
AUGUST	3°	4.5702	5.8418	82.99%
SEPTEMBER	13°	5.0711	6.4738	85.39%
OCTOBER	23°	5.0053	6.6100	85.72%
NOVEMBER	27°	5.6170	7.2666	86.55%
DECEMBER	27°	5.8298	7.7846	86.49%
		5.6645	86.1479	83.82%
PERCENTAGE IMPROVEMENT		0.85%	10.32%	1.94%

Table 23: Table indicating the performance of the plant with a monthly change in the tilt.

Result:

Improvements:

Figure 62: Graph representing the performance of the plant with a monthly change in the tilt.

1. There is an increase in the amount of solar irradiation received throughout the year by changing the tilt angles every month, hence resulting in an increase in the performance ratio
2. Total number of million units generated throughout the year is greater when compared to the existing tilt arrangement.

Potential problems:

1. The installation and maintenance of this arrangement is more complex than a two tilt arrangement.
2. For a huge solar PV plant the changing of tilts of the panels the losses incurred due to damage of panels caused by stresses and miss-handling by personnel during frequent change of tilts of the panels is significant.
3. Practically feasibility must be determined by doing a cost benefit analysis, as monthly tilt variation is usually not practised in larger PV plants.

3.4.4.2 SUGGESTION 2: CHANGING TILT ANGLES SEASONALLY

Calculations are done and a table comparing the tilt irradiance received, energy generated and the resultant performance ratio is shown along with the yearly percentage improvement from each parameter. Here, the tilt suggested is changed seasonally during summer (7°/10°), monsoon (3°), and winter (27°).

For a summer tilt of 7°:

SUGGESTION 2 : CHANGING TILT ANGLES SEASONALLY				
MONTH	TILT SUGGESTED	TILT IRRADIATION	ENERGY GENERATED	PERFORMANCE RATIO (%)
		kWh/m².day	Million units(MU)	
MARCH-MAY(SUMMER)	7°	6.18436087	23.612855	83.26%
JUNE-SEPTEMBER(MONSOON)	3°	4.818755738	24.202588	82.84%
OCTOBER-FEBRUARY(WINTER)	27°	5.968774834	38.492886	85.79%
		5.657297147	86.308329	83.96%
PERCENTAGE IMPROVEMENT		0.72%	10.53%	2.12%

Table 24: Table indicating the performance of the plant with a seasonal change in the tilt-7° for the months of March-May

For a summer tilt of 10°:

SUGGESTION 2 : CHANGING TILT ANGLES SEASONALLY				
MONTH	TILT SUGGESTED	TILT IRRADIATION	ENERGY GENERATED	PERFORMANCE RATIO (%)
		kWh/m ² .day	Million units(MU)	
MARCH-MAY(SUMMER)	10°	6.186970652	22.513363	79.62%
JUNE-SEPTEMBER(MONSOON)	3°	4.818755738	24.202588	82.84%
OCTOBER-FEBRUARY(WINTER)	27°	5.968774834	38.492886	85.79%
		5.658167075	85.208837	82.75%
PERCENTAGE IMPROVEMENT		0.74%	9.12%	0.64%

Table 25: Table indicating the performance of the plant with a seasonal change in the tilt-10° for the months of March-May

Result:

Figure 63: Graph representing the performance of the plant with a seasonal change in the tilt (7° for the months of March-May)

Figure 64: Graph indicating a comparison between the current two tilt arrangement and the proposed three tilt arrangement (7° for the months of March-May) for the tilt irradiation received

Selecting 7° tilt for the summer months (March-May):

1. It is observed that for the proposed three tilt arrangement with a 7° summer tilt, the average solar irradiation received throughout the year increases by 0.72%. When compared to the value obtained using two tilt arrangement, the performance ratio increases by 2.12%
2. Total number of million units generated also increases by a significant 10.53%.

Figure 65: Graph representing the performance of the plant with a seasonal change in the tilt (10° for the months of March-May)

Figure 66: Graph indicating a comparison between the current two tilt arrangement and the proposed three tilt arrangement (10° for the months of March-May) for the tilt irradiation received.

Selecting 10° tilt for the summer months (March-May):

1. It is observed that the average solar irradiation received throughout the year increases by 0.74% compared to the value obtained using two tilt arrangement, the performance ratio increases by 0.64%
2. The total number of million units generated increases by 9.12%.

Advantage of using this mechanism:

A summer tilt of 7° is clearly preferable to a 10° tilt according to the overall energy generated as well as the PR of the plant over a year from a comparative analysis of Table 3 and Table 4. However a greater tilt irradiance is received on solar panels due to a 10° tilt during summer months compared to a 7° tilt.

It is realised that an increase in the solar irradiation does not have a linear relation with number of tilt angles as environmental factors also play a major role in impacting the net million units generated. By changing the tilt arrangement from a two tilt system to a three tilt system a significant improvement in average irradiation , performance ratio, and net million units generated is observed; the installation complexity and maintenance for the this tilt arrangement increases slightly but the performance improvement outweighs the challenges faced to adopt a three tilt arrangement.

3.4.5 CONCLUSION:

For the optimization of the system with an increment in the overall output of the plant a three tilt arrangement system can be opted with the following tilting angles:

March-May: 7° or 10 °

June-September: 3°

October-February: 27°

**CHAPTER 4 -
CONCLUSION & FUTURE
SCOPE**

A set of viable, site specific proposals were suggested to TPSSL to optimize the long-term performance of an existing 50 MW solar photovoltaic plant. The following proposals were suggested.

4.1 Improvement 1: PV panel cleaning system using Mist nozzle

The objective of the proposal is to minimize the large quantity of water needed for cleaning of the solar panels in the grid-connected system. A cleaning system has been designed using a mist nozzle spray and trough collector combined with the conventional methods used at the plant. A 3-D CAD model has been developed and flow simulation has been performed for the same using SOLIDWORKS software. 8933.36 litres of water is saved per day in this system.

4.2 Improvement 2: Site-specific suggestion for a Three-tilt (PV panel) arrangement

Incidence angle of the sunlight varies throughout the year due to the rotation of the earth around its own axis and its elliptical orbit. Optimum fixed tilt angles of PV panels should be changed monthly and seasonally in order to extract maximum power[2]. Factors affecting power generation at a panel level, include tilt irradiation (GII), soiling losses, shading losses, module temperature, among others which vary as the tilt of the mounted panel changes.

A simulation considering all these factors was run for a variety of tilt angles ranging from 3°-27 ° for a span of one year. Two new tilt angles were obtained for the same duration, and the total increase in generation was found to be 9.14%-10.53% for 0.74%-0.72% increase in radiation. Depending on the requirements of the plant, a suitable value can be chosen.

4.3 Improvement 3: Proposal for Automating the Lighting and Fan circuit

The Power Plant is spread widely over 504 acres of land consisting about 26 pre-engineered buildings (PEBs) which have connected lighting and fan circuits along with other auxiliary supply needs. These buildings are placed at a significant distance from each other as well as the main control room. In order to address this issue an IoT based control module was designed and a prototype was developed, based on the layout and existing wiring scheme of the inverter rooms.

4.4 Improvement 4: Proposal for reduction in near shading of the PV panel

Near shading occurs due to surrounding growth of grass, causing anywhere from 15%-20% of the PV panel's surface area throughout the year in spite of efforts to periodically cut grass. In order to combat the electrical and irradiance losses caused as a result, an organic weed control is suggested. A combination of 10% vinegar and salt was proposed, which is an organic contact herbicide, suitable for government regulations. PV Array power improvement in the range of 1612 KW - 5010 KW can be obtained using this suggestion.

4.5. Future Scope

An overall enhancement of the performance of the power plant was attained along with a projected reduction in running costs. The suggested improvements were well received by TPSSL as possible solutions for the current scenario at their power plant.

The suggested improvements can also be adapted for use in similar already existing large scale solar PV installations. Common operational and maintenance problems faced in such systems will have viable solutions, which can help in obtaining an overall optimization of the PV plant performance.

**CHAPTER: 5 - GLOSSARY
OF TERMS AND
ABBREVIATIONS**

GLOSSARY OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

- CUF-capacity utilization factor (%)
- DHI_d-daily sum of diffuse radiation (kW h/m²)
- E_Grid-energy injected in to grid
- E_A-array energy output per day
- E_{Array}-effective energy at the output of the array
- EffArrR-efficient E_{out} array/rough area
- EffsysR-efficient E_{out} system/rough area
- E_{sd}-daily sum of specific electricity produced (kW h/kW p)
- E_{share}-percentual share of monthly electricity produced (%)
- E_{sm}-monthly sum of specific electricity produced (kW h/kW p)
- E_{tm}-monthly sum of total electricity produced (GWh)
- G₀-global irradiance at STC (W/m²)
- GHI_d-daily sum of global irradiation (kW h/m²)
- GHI_m-monthly sum of global irradiation (kW h/m²)
- GlobEff-effective global irradiance
- GlobHor-horizontal global irradiation
- GlobInc-global incident in coll. Plane
- H_{inv}-inverter efficiency (%)
- H_t-total Horizontal irradiance on array plane (Wh/m²)
- I_{dc}-DC current (A)
- I_{mpp} : Output Current of PV string at MPP point
- I_{oc}-Short circuit ratio
- L_C-Array capture loss

L_{CM} -miscellaneous capture losses

L_{CT} -thermal capture losses

L_T : Losses due to temperature

NTPC-National Thermal Power Corporation

P: Output power from PV string at MPP

P_0 -Nominal Power at STC

PR-performance ratio (%)

PV-photovoltaic

RI_d -daily sum of reflected radiation (kW h/m²)

Shloss-losses of global irradiation by terrain shading (%)

STC-standard conditions 25 °C, 1000W/m²; A.M. = 1.5

T_{Amb} -ambient temperature

T_{24} -daily air temperature (°C)

V_{dc} -DC voltage (V)

V_{mpp} :Output Voltage of PV string at MPP point

V_{OC} -open circuit voltage

W/m² is the irradiance received at solar panel

Y_A -array yield (h/d)

Y_F -final yield (h/d)

Y_R -reference yield (h/d)

$\eta_{PV,T}$ -PV module global efficiency factor (%)

$\eta_{sys,T}$ -total system efficiency (%)

CHAPTER: 6 - REFERENCES

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